

SCHOOL OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES

Women and Fishing in Ohio

A Report from the Environment and Social Sustainability Lab

THE OHIO STATE UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF FOOD, AGRICULTURAL,
AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

About the Environmental and Social Sustainability Lab

The Environmental and Social Sustainability (ESS) Lab is a collaborative community of scholars working to build scientific understanding of environmental and social sustainability in an interdisciplinary context. Housed within the School of Environmental and Natural Resources within The College of Food, Agriculture, and Environmental Sciences, we are staffed by a core group of affiliated faculty members, students, and research staff representing a broad range of social science expertise. Our mission is to support a viable socio-ecological future through applied social science research, and to serve as a hub of sustainability research at Ohio State.

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Executive Summary

Background

In the United States, participation in fishing is more than twice as common among men than women, suggesting both a gap and an opportunity for agencies tasked with managing resources for the benefit of their citizens¹. Outdoor recreational activities such as fishing can improve quality of life for women, by cultivating positive self-perception, a better sense of life balance, and an increased sense of belonging². Likewise, improving recreational opportunities for women may enhance opportunity (e.g., their dependents) for others as well³. Moreover, increased participation in fishing ultimately improves the resources available for fisheries conservation and for agencies like the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Division of Wildlife (ODNR–DOW) through increased license sales and the resources they generate. In this study, we surveyed male and female Ohio license holders and Ohio residents to assess potential differences in fishing participation between genders, and likewise identify factors associated with participation and non-participation among women.

Methods in Brief

To assess differences between male and female license holders, we selected a sample of half men and half women license holders who purchased a fishing license in 2023 and had a valid email address on file with ODNR-ODW. Licensed respondents were further stratified by number of years they purchased a license in the previous 4 to account for the tendency of avid anglers to respond at higher rates than less avid anglers (see full Methodology section for greater detail). To understand differences between women who fish and women who do not typically

¹ U.S. Department of Interior, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, and U.S. Department of Commerce, U.S. Census Bureau. 2018. 2016 National Survey of Fishing, Hunting, and Wildlife-Associated Recreation. Page 17.

² Lloyd, K., and D. E. Little. 2005. "Quality of life, aren't we always searching for that?": How women can achieve enhanced quality of life through participation in outdoor adventure recreation. *Leisure/Loisir* 29(2):147–181.

³ Henderson, K. A. 1994. Broadening an Understanding of Women, Gender, and Leisure. *Journal of Leisure Research* 26(1):1–7.

fish, we sampled Ohioans via an online convenience sample managed by Qualtrics, and enforced a quota for respondents of half women and half men. This sample was originally stratified by 1) residents in counties adjacent to Lake Erie and 2) residents in all other Ohio counties, however, analyses presented here are weighted to reflect all Ohioans. All surveys were conducted online via the Qualtrics platforming spring 2024.

Study Findings

Family Participation: Most respondents reported having no children at home; however, for those who do, children accompany adults on outdoor trips at least half the time. Notably, women anglers in both samples were more likely to have children at home, and licensed women reported taking children along on nearly 71% of their trips (Figure A). By comparison, licensed men took a slightly lower percentage of recreational trips with kids (64%; for full comparison, see Excel summary of results). This suggests that when children are present, outdoor trips have a strong family dynamic, which could be leveraged for family-oriented programming.

Figure A. Comparison of a sample of licensed women anglers, self-identified women anglers from a public sample, women recreationists who did not fish in Ohio in the previous year but participated in another outdoor activity, and women in Ohio who did not participate in any outdoor activity in Ohio in the previous year. Trips refer to the estimated percent of recreational trips taken with kids.

Interest in Increasing Outdoor Participation: A sizable number of Ohioans expressed interest in increasing the time they spend participating in outdoor recreational activities. This may be particularly important for women, for whom participation in fishing was associated with an enhanced sense of life meaning. That

is, the development of initiatives that promote outdoor activities may, in turn, boost overall well-being, at least among women.

Environmental Stewardship: On average, Ohioans identify to some degree as environmentalists and conservationists—with license holders averaging slightly stronger identification than the public overall, potentially due to deeper engagement with the outdoors. To the extent that identifying as an environmentalist or conservationist aligns with stewardship values, there may be an opportunity to develop conservation messaging and, via partnerships with community organizations, better engage Ohioans in in stewardship activities.

Reliance on Public Access: Most anglers do not own boats, suggesting some reliance on access sites for their fishing activities. This highlights the importance of continued maintenance and enhancement of public access points and associated facilities.

Gender Findings: Women across samples were more likely than men to target “anything that bites” during fishing, suggesting they are less likely to be seeking specialized fishing experiences. Interestingly, aside from some specific targeting differences and activity participation rates, male and female anglers share many similarities in their outdoor experiences. For example, regardless of gender or sample, anglers on average agreed that fishing is one of the most enjoyable activities they do.

Broader Recreational Preferences: In addition to fishing, hiking and walking emerged as the most popular outdoor recreational activities among both men and women. However, women in the public sample were less likely than their male counterparts to participate in hunting, fishing, or camping, suggesting that tailored outreach could help bridge this participation gap.

Recommendations

1. **Prioritize Family-Friendly Programs**

Given that children often accompany outdoor trips—especially among women anglers—agencies could foster participation through family-centric events and educational programs. Initiatives such as guided fishing days, youth camps, and family safety workshops can strengthen intergenerational bonds and promote outdoor enjoyment.

2. **Continue/Strengthen Partnerships for Cross-Agency Safety Initiatives:**
Addressing safety concerns is important across all demographics for both anglers and participants in other outdoor recreation. Collaborations with Ohio State Parks & Watercraft to offer boat and water safety informational sessions may alleviate some fishing-specific concerns. Working with law enforcement across divisions and jurisdictions to provide public safety tips may create a comprehensive support network that addresses broader concerns about safety in remote areas and encourages broader participation.
3. **Enhance Public Access and Facilities:**
With a substantial portion of anglers relying on public access for boating and other activities, continued investment in and maintenance of public access points should be an ongoing priority to promote participation. Improving these facilities will ensure that all community members have safe and reliable ways to enjoy the outdoors.
4. **Targeted Outreach to Expand Participation:**
The expressed desire among Ohioans to boost outdoor recreation participation presents an opportunity to develop specific initiatives that engage women. Outreach strategies might include promotional campaigns that highlight the health, social, and environmental benefits of outdoor activities broadly and fishing specifically. Continued investment in tailored workshops and community events like Ohio Women's Outdoor Adventure that feature multiple activities like hiking, fishing, and environmental education may bring new women outdoors and support ODW's mission to better serve all Ohioans.
5. **Leverage Conservation Values:**
Since many outdoor enthusiasts already identify as environmentalists and conservationists, agencies can integrate conservation education into all programming. Aligning conservation messaging with recreational events can reinforce the community's environmental commitment and encourage stewardship of natural resources.

Methodology and Design

This study was organized and administered by members of the Environmental and Social Sustainability (ESS) Lab in the School of Environment and Natural Resources, in collaboration with the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, Division of Wildlife (ODNR–DOW).

Survey Design and Sampling

To understand how to both better serve women who fish (such that they continue fishing) and what factors might encourage other women in Ohio to fish, we sampled two populations: 1) fishing license holders from Ohio's Wildlife Licensing System, and 2) an online panel of residents from Ohio (see sections below for sampling details). Online surveys were sent to both sample groups during March and April of 2024. Respondents were asked about previous outdoor recreational pursuits, where they typically seek information about outdoor recreation, and if they participated in fishing in Ohio in the previous 12 months. Respondents who fished in Ohio in the past 12 months were directed to a series of questions assessing their general fishing activities, additional details about their most recent fishing trip, and finally to a set of demographic questions. Respondents who did not fish in Ohio in the past 12 months were asked if they participated in at least one outdoor recreational activity in Ohio in the past 12 months. Respondents who participated in at least one type of outdoor recreational activity were directed to a set of questions similar to those asked of individuals who reported fishing (i.e., questions on general participation in the activity they participated in most recently and detailed questions about their most recent trip) and then asked the same set of demographic questions. Any respondents who did not participate in *any* outdoor activities in Ohio in the past 12 months were sent directly to the demographics section of the survey.

License holder sample: The license sample group consisted of all anglers who purchased a 2023 resident fishing license (i.e. one-year, one-day, three-day, or lifetime resident license) and had a valid email address on file with the Ohio Division of Wildlife. To ensure adequate representation of female anglers, the group was stratified such that ½ of the sampled individuals were male and ½ female (according

to the sex on file) and further stratified by the number of years the license holder purchase a license of the previous four years (i.e., 2019–2023; Table 1). The strata defined by purchase history were grouped as follows: license holders who *only* purchased a license in 2023 were identified as fishing one of the prior five years, anglers who purchased a license in 2023 and in one other prior year were identified as fishing two of five years, and so on (see Table M1). License holders were divided by sex to obtain equal proportions of male and female anglers in the sample as follows:

*Table M1. Sampling strata, desired sample sizes, and expected response rates.**

Number of years fished	No Incentive Used			Incentive Used		
	Expected response rate*	Desired count	Estimated sample**	Expected response rate*	Desired count	Estimated sample**
1	0.04	80	2100	0.08	80	1100
2	0.08	80	1100	0.16	80	600
3	0.09	80	989	0.18	80	544
4	0.14	80	671	0.28	80	386
5	0.20	80	500	0.40	80	300
Total		400	5360		400	2930

*Obtained from Kulupparachchi et al. under review

**Represents the estimated sample from each year as an equal proportion of male and female anglers

The survey also evaluated the use of monetary incentives as mentioned above (i.e., a \$10 gift card) to determine their usefulness for increasing response rates. In total, 5360 surveys were sent in the ‘no-incentive’ group and 2930 surveys sent in the ‘incentive group’. We received 667 responses for an overall response rate of 9% (Table M2). To account for the oversample of women, subsequent analyses for the licensed sample overall (but not the gender-specific analyses) are weighted to reflect the actual proportion of women in the license database (24% female).

Table M2. Response rates to the survey - by all anglers, male and female.

Groupings	Total responses count	Response rates by group	Male response rates	Female response rates
Incentive Group				
Incentive	244	8%	4%	4%
No Incentive	428	7%	4%	3%
License Purchased Years				
1 year	192	6%	3%	3%
2 years	117	7%	4%	4%
3 years	138	9%	5%	5%
4 years	115	11%	7%	5%
5 years	105	13%	9%	6%
Total	667	9%	5%	4%

General public sample: We drew the public sample from an online survey panel managed by Qualtrics, who provides modest incentives for online respondents to surveys. We used quotas aimed at securing 540 responses from the counties bordering Lake Erie (Erie), and 540 responses from the counties in the rest of Ohio (ROH), divided evenly (50/50) between men and women for each region. We received a total of 1110 responses (Erie N = 569, ROH N = 541). All subsequent analyses in this report for the public sample are weighted to reflect Ohioans overall (Erie counties comprise 21% of Ohio's population and thus are downweighted for these analyses).

Section 1: Demographics

Age, Education, and Income

Respondents in both the license and public samples were asked to indicate the year in which they were born, which was subtracted from 2024 to produce their age at the time of the survey. Where license holder age data was missing, age at sale (2023) was drawn from the license holder database and was merged into the survey data to facilitate analyses. Average age across both samples for men and women was 48–52 years old (Table 1), though public women who did not participate in any outdoor recreation tended to be older (59 years old; see Supplementary Excel file).

Education was assessed via a scale ranging from less than a high school diploma to graduate or professional degree. Similar percentages of licensed women and men held a bachelor's degree or higher (40–41%), while fewer public women (23%) and men (25%) held a bachelor's degree or higher (Table 1). Annual household income before taxes was assessed via typical scales, binning income ranges from less than \$10,000 to \$200,000 or more. Slightly fewer licensed women (52%) than men (57%) reported an income of over \$75,000/year, while just 25% of public women and men reported an income over \$75,000/year (Table 1).

Finally, we asked respondents which best described their employment status (e.g., employed, unemployed, care provider, etc.). While around 2 in 3 license holders were employed full time (women: 63%; men: 64%), fewer public women (32%) and men (37%) respondents were employed full time (Table 1)⁴. For further detail on estimated hours per week spent on paid work vs. other activities, see Supplementary Excel file.

⁴ Women in our data indicating any employment (full- or part-time), as well as those seeking employment would be counted as part of the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (USBLS) “labor force” statistic (see here: <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/wb/data/county-state-labor-force-participation>). According to the USBLS, for women in Ohio that number is 75%, while in the public sample we collected for this study, it is 53%. Licensed women in the present study were at 72% labor force participation, and women who fish in the public sample were at 62%. Note, however, given the compilation of categories, the “labor force” number conceals some nuance that may matter for understanding recreation participation.

Table 1. Age, education, and income for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (% or Mean (SD) as appropriate)			General Public Sample (% or Mean (SD) as appropriate)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Age	48 (15.3)	49 (15.9)	49 (15.7)	50 (16.6)	52 (17.4)	51 (17.0)
How much formal education have you completed?						
Less than high school diploma	0.5%	2.8%	1.7%	4.7%	6.2%	5.4%
High school diploma or equivalent (for example, GED)	12.7%	20.5%	16.8%	30.4%	30.6%	30.5%
Some college, no degree	29.9%	24.7%	26.9%	27.6%	23.9%	25.8%
Associate's degree	17.3%	11.2%	14.2%	14.1%	11.2%	12.6%
Bachelor's degree	22.3%	23.7%	23.1%	14.2%	20.0%	17.0%
Graduate or professional degree	17.3%	17.2%	17.3%	9.0%	8.2%	8.7%
What is your annual household income from all sources before taxes?						
Less than \$10,000	1.7%	2.5%	2.3%	12.9%	9.8%	11.4%
\$10,000 - \$14,999	1.1%	1.5%	1.4%	7.7%	6.6%	7.2%
\$15,000 - \$24,999	4.4%	5.4%	5.2%	8.8%	8.9%	8.9%
\$25,000 - \$34,999	7.2%	1.0%	2.3%	15.3%	11.3%	13.4%
\$35,000 - \$49,999	14.4%	11.8%	12.6%	15.0%	17.8%	16.3%
\$50,000 - \$74,999	18.2%	21.1%	20.5%	15.9%	20.3%	18.0%
\$75,000 - \$99,999	23.2%	14.7%	16.5%	11.2%	14.2%	12.6%
\$100,000 - \$149,999	16.0%	18.6%	18.1%	8.2%	7.2%	7.7%
\$150,000 - \$199,999	7.2%	12.3%	11.2%	2.9%	2.6%	2.8%
\$200,000 or more	5.5%	11.3%	10.1%	2.2%	1.1%	1.7%
What best describes your employment status?						
Employed (full time)	62.6%	64.1%	63.7%	32.2%	36.7%	34.4%
Unemployed (looking for work)	1.0%	2.3%	2.0%	6.6%	11.0%	8.7%
Retired	15.9%	28.6%	25.9%	25.2%	29.5%	27.2%
Care provider	4.1%	0.0%	1.5%	6.4%	1.2%	4.0%
Employed (part time)	9.2%	2.8%	4.2%	14.1%	12.2%	13.2%
Student	1.0%	0.9%	0.9%	4.2%	1.7%	3.0%
Unemployed (unable to work)	3.1%	1.4%	1.7%	11.3%	7.7%	9.5%

Rurality of current residence vs. place where respondent grew up

Respondents were asked to select a description of the residence or community in which they grew up, ranging from a large city with 250,000 or more people to a farm or rural area. Licensed responses for both men and women slightly skewed toward smaller towns and rural areas, while public responses for both men and women tended toward larger towns and cities (Table 2).

Public respondents were asked to provide their ZIP code of residence, while residence ZIP codes for license holders were imported from the license database. ZIP codes were then used to assign all respondents to a Rural-Urban Commuting Area Code (RUCA⁵), which is a census tract-based classification system that uses standard census measures of population density and other variables to characterize all U.S. census tracts to a rural/urban status. Between 70–74% of licensed respondents lived in urban areas, while 73–82% of public respondents lived in an urban area (Table 2).

⁵ See for RUCA categorizations (old home): <https://depts.washington.edu/uwruca/ruca-uses.php>; and USDA use of RUCA and updates on fresh estimates for 2020: <https://www.ers.usda.gov/data-products/rural-urban-commuting-area-codes.aspx>; future home for RUCA codes: <https://www.ers.usda.gov/data-products/rural-urban-commuting-area-codes.aspx>

Table 2. Current and childhood rurality for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample			General Public Sample		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
How would you describe the residence or community where you grew up?						
Large city with 250,000 or more people	9.6%	9.6%	9.6%	15.7%	17.6%	16.6%
City with 100,000-249,999 people	6.6%	7.3%	7.2%	12.1%	12.2%	12.2%
City with 50,000-99,999 people	13.2%	11.4%	11.8%	14.2%	13.8%	14.1%
Small city with 25,000-49,999 people	16.8%	14.6%	15.1%	16.5%	16.2%	16.4%
Town with 10,000-24,999 people	12.2%	16.9%	15.9%	10.1%	9.3%	9.7%
Town with 5,000-9,999 people	8.6%	7.8%	7.9%	6.2%	10.5%	8.3%
Small town/village with less than 5,000 people	16.2%	14.6%	15.0%	12.0%	10.4%	11.3%
Current residence by RUCA C categorization						
Rural	26.0%	29.8%	28.9%	26.2%	17.6%	22.0%
Urban	74.0%	70.2%	71.1%	73.8%	82.4%	78.0%

Children at home and percent of recreation spent with children

All respondents were asked how many children under the age of 18 lived in their home, with possible responses limited to 0, 1, 2, 3, or “4 or more”. Most women and men respondents across both samples reported 0 children at home under the age of 18 (66–77%; Table 4), though this varied by age, such that people aged 35-54 reported having children at home at higher levels than other age groups across samples (Table 3). Respondents who reported having 1 or more children at home under 18 were asked, “What percentage of your recreation trips were with your kid(s)?” On average, license holding women reported the highest percentage (71%) while public men reported the lowest (53%; Table 4).

Table 3. Percent respondents with 1 or more children at home by binned age groups in the license holder sample and public sample.

Sample	Age	% of sample in binned age	% of sample with 1+ children at home and in binned age	
License	Overall	18–34	17.6%	4.8%
		35–54	39.3%	23.6%
		55+	43.2%	2.8%
	Women	18–34	20.2%	6.4%
		35–54	52.1%	27.7%
		55+	27.7%	0.0%
	Men	18–34	17.1%	4.7%
		35–54	35.6%	22.4%
		55+	47.4%	3.5%
Public	Overall	18–34	20.4%	9.6%
		35–54	34.8%	15.3%
		55+	44.8%	3.0%
	Women	18–34	21.6%	11.8%
		35–54	35.5%	17.1%
		55+	42.9%	3.1%
	Men	18–34	18.9%	7.0%
		35–54	34.1%	13.5%
		55+	47.0%	2.9%

Table 4. Children at home and percent of recreation spent with children among respondents with 1 or more children at home for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (% or Mean (SD) as appropriate)			General Public Sample (% or Mean (SD) as appropriate)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Number of children at home under 18						
0	66.3%	69.4%	68.7%	67.9%	76.5%	72.0%
1	11.1%	9.6%	9.9%	15.4%	11.2%	13.4%
2	12.6%	13.7%	13.5%	10.3%	7.3%	8.9%
3	6.5%	4.1%	4.6%	3.1%	2.3%	2.7%
4 or more	3.5%	3.2%	3.3%	3.2%	2.8%	3.0%
What percentage of your recreation trips were with your kid(s)? (Answered if they reported kids at home)	71.1 (31.19)	64.1 (33.28)	65.8 (32.79)	59.2 (37.89)	53.2 (36.76)	56.8 (37.50)

Preferred amount of recreation and perceived support

All respondents were asked if they would prefer for their time spent participating in outdoor recreation increased, decreased, or stayed the same in the coming 12 months. For both women and men, most license holders preferred their recreation to increase (74–77%), while half of public women (51%) and slightly fewer public men (44%) preferred an increase in their recreation (Table 5), signaling an area of opportunity to engage more people in the outdoors broadly, and perhaps fishing specifically.

We wanted to better understand factors that may hinder outdoor recreation among women and asked all respondents on a scale of extremely unsupported (1) to extremely supported (5), to what degree they felt supported in pursuing their preferred amount of outdoor recreational time. Averages across men and women for both samples hovered around the midpoint (3), with licensed women respondents averaging the highest perceived support ($M = 3.85$; $SD = 1.12$) and public men the lowest ($M = 3.43$; $SD = 1.04$; Table 5; see Appendix A for scale distribution of responses).

Table 5. Preferred recreation amount and perceived support for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (% or Mean (SD) as appropriate)			General Public Sample (% or Mean (SD) as appropriate)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
When considering the amount of time you spent participating in outdoor recreation over the past 12 months, would you prefer if it decreased, increased, or stayed the same in the next 12 months?						
Decrease	3.0%	1.80%	2.1%	10.4%	7.3%	9.0%
Stay the same	22.7%	20.90%	21.3%	39.1%	49.0%	43.8%
Increase	74.2%	77.30%	76.6%	50.5%	43.7%	47.3%
To what degree do you feel supported in pursuing the amount of outdoor recreational time you would like? (1=Extremely unsupported to 5=Extremely supported)						
	3.85 (1.12)	3.61 (1.09)	3.66 (1.10)	3.57 (1.03)	3.43 (1.04)	3.50 (1.04)

Conservation-related identities and sense of meaning in life

Social identities shape beliefs and behaviors around both outdoor recreation and conservation^{6,7}. All respondents were asked to rate their level of identification with several conservation and recreation related identities on a scale of not at all (1) to very strongly (5). Both women (M = 2.83; SD = 1.21) and men (M = 3.52; SD = 1.20) licensed respondents rated their identification as an angler/fisherman higher than other identities, while women and men in the public sample had an average identity rating of 2.5 or below across all identities (Table 6; see Appendix A for scale distribution of responses).

To understand the potential impact of outdoor recreation on personal well-being, respondents were asked to rate 3 statements⁸ about their felt meaning in life on a scale of not at all (1) to completely (11). Licensed respondents generally reported feeling more meaning in life overall, and women averaged higher responses than men both for leading a purposeful and meaningful life, and that what they do in life is valuable and worthwhile (Table 6; see Appendix A for scale distribution of responses). Public respondents averaged at least 1 point lower for these questions compared to licensed respondents, but again public women averaged higher responses than public men both for leading a purposeful and meaningful life, and that what they do in life is valuable and worthwhile (Table 6; see Appendix A for scale distribution of responses).

⁶ Bruskotter, J. T., Vucetich, J. A., Dietsch, A., Slagle, K. M., Brooks, J. S., & Nelson, M. P. (2019). Conservationists' moral obligations toward wildlife: values and identity promote conservation conflict. *Biological Conservation*, 240, 108296.

⁷ Toth, J. F., & Brown, R. B. (1997). Racial and gender meanings of why people participate in recreational fishing. *Leisure Sciences*, 19(2), 129–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490409709512244>

⁸ "Meaning" dimension of the PERMA profiler: <https://www.internationaljournalofwellbeing.org/index.php/ijow/article/view/526>. Correlates well to "flourishing," another commonly used measure of well-being: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11205-009-9493-y#appendices>.

Table 6. Conservation related identities and sense of meaning in life men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (Mean (SD))			General Public Sample (Mean (SD))		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Average identity as... (1=Not at all to 5=Very strongly)						
Hunter	1.63 (1.15)	2.63 (1.50)	2.41 (1.50)	1.33 (0.87)	1.77 (1.18)	1.54 (1.05)
Environmentalist	2.69 (1.19)	2.85 (1.19)	2.82 (1.19)	2.19 (1.19)	2.39 (1.19)	2.28 (1.19)
Conservationist	2.72 (1.23)	3.14 (1.15)	3.05 (1.18)	2.17 (1.15)	2.44 (1.14)	2.30 (1.15)
Farmer/rancher	1.71 (1.14)	1.73 (1.09)	1.72 (1.10)	1.45 (1.03)	1.50 (0.95)	1.47 (0.99)
Angler/Fisherman	2.83 (1.21)	3.52 (1.20)	3.37 (1.24)	1.62 (1.06)	2.15 (1.26)	1.88 (1.19)
Meaning: In general, to what extent do you lead a purposeful and meaningful life? (1 = Not at all to 11 = Completely)						
	9.34 (1.80)	9.14 (2.30)	9.19 (2.28)	8.33 (2.26)	8.02 (2.48)	8.18 (2.37)
Meaning: In general, to what extent do you feel that what you do in your life is valuable and worthwhile? (1 = Not at all to 11 = Completely)						
	9.51 (1.85)	9.01 (2.53)	9.14 (2.46)	8.39 (2.37)	8.00 (2.61)	8.21 (2.49)
Meaning: To what extent do you generally feel you have a sense of direction in your life? (1 = Not at all to 11 = Completely)						
	8.97 (2.04)	8.94 (2.56)	8.96 (2.51)	8.00 (2.40)	7.98 (2.74)	7.99 (2.57)

Section 2: Fishing Activities

Fishing Behavior

All respondents were asked if they went fishing in Ohio in the past 12 months, and 93–96% of licensed respondents responded that they had purchased a license, while 16% of public women respondents and 24% of public men respondents reported the same (Table 7).

Table 7. Fishing participation in previous 12 months for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (% or Mean (SD) Median as appropriate)			General Public Sample (% or Mean (SD) Median as appropriate)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Did you go fishing in Ohio the past 12 months?						
Yes, and I purchased a license	95.6%	92.7%	93.3%	15.8%	23.6%	19.5%
Yes, but I fished in a private lake/pond (Pay Lake) and did not purchase a license	1.6%	1.6%	1.6%	19.8%	12.7%	16.4%
No, but I fished in another state/country	0.6%	1.3%	1.1%	3.5%	5.3%	4.4%
No, I did not fish in Ohio or anywhere else	2.2%	4.5%	3.9%	60.9%	58.4%	59.7%
How many fishing trips did you take in the past 12 months to fish for any type of fish in Ohio? (0-100; answers greater than 100 removed from analysis)*						
	17 (17.1)	19 (17.8)	19 (17.7)	16 (18.5)	19 (20.2)	17 (19.5)
	11	13	12	9	11	10

*This analysis is limited to respondents who chose either of the “Yes” options for the “Did you go fishing in Ohio in the past 12 months” question.

Respondents who reported fishing in Ohio in the previous 12 months were asked in which of the previous 5 years they fished in Ohio (regardless of license purchase). A majority of licensed women (63%) and men (71%) respondents reported fishing all years (2019–2023), while around half of public women (50%) and public men (58%) reported fishing in all years (Table 7). The same respondents were asked if they owned a boat that was used for fishing, and around half of licensed women (53%) and men (53%) respondents reported no boat ownership, while 75% of public women and 68% of public men reported the same. Respondents who fished in Ohio in the previous 12 months reported how frequently they fished several Ohio waterbodies. The Ohio River and pay lakes were the least fished waterbodies among license holding respondents, with heavy majorities of women (80% Ohio River; 91% pay lake) and men (83% Ohio River; 92% pay lake) reporting never fishing those waterbody types. Public respondents reported never having fished the Ohio River and pay lakes at much lower rates (52–58%), however, suggesting some differences between the license holders who respond to fishing surveys and the fishing general public (Table 8; see Appendix A for scaled frequency distribution of responses by waterbody).

Table 8. Years fished, boat ownership, and reports of never having fished a waterbody for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample			General Public Sample		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
In which of the following years did you fish in Ohio? (Select all that apply.)						
2019	31.3%	23.6%	36.0%	33.3%	38.7%	36.0%
2020	31.7%	23.6%	35.8%	32.9%	38.7%	35.8%
2021	35.3%	27.9%	39.1%	36.7%	41.6%	39.1%
2022	44.6%	34.5%	43.1%	41.3%	45.0%	43.1%
2023	60.1%	46.5%	54.2%	53.6%	54.9%	54.2%
All years (2019-2023)	62.6%	70.9%	53.7%	50.0%	57.5%	53.7%
Do you own a boat that is used for fishing?						
No	52.7%	53.2%	46.8%	74.7%	67.6%	71.3%
Yes, paddle boat (e.g. Canoe, Kayak)	23.3%	22.5%	22.7%	13.3%	15.0%	14.1%
Yes, motor boat (i.e. anything with gasoline engine)	30.4%	28.8%	29.3%	13.5%	19.6%	16.4%
How often did you fish each type of water body in the past 12 months? (Percentages for "Never fished" reported)						
Lake Erie	52.2%	44.0%	46.0%	49.8%	38.2%	44.1%
Lake Erie Tributary	77.6%	64.5%	67.7%	70.8%	57.8%	64.4%
Ohio River	79.8%	82.8%	82.1%	53.8%	51.8%	52.8%
Ohio inland river or stream (NOT the Ohio River)	45.7%	41.7%	42.7%	50.4%	41.5%	46.0%
Ohio inland lake or reservoir	20.6%	24.3%	23.4%	32.4%	28.8%	30.7%
Pond	27.1%	28.4%	28.1%	20.1%	27.7%	23.7%
Pay Lakes	90.5%	92.1%	91.7%	58.4%	52.7%	55.7%

Recent trips

Respondents who reported fishing in Ohio in the previous 12 months were asked to provide several details regarding their most recent trip. First, respondents were asked to indicate which species they fished for in Ohio most frequently in the previous 12 months (including an option for “Anything that bites”). Women across the two samples were more likely to target anything that bites than men. Among the public, Largemouth, Smallmouth, and Spotted Bass were the most frequently fished species (9–18%; Table 9). Some species were pursued by a very small number of respondents (i.e., Muskellunge and Northern Pike), so estimates for related survey items should be interpreted with caution.

Table 9. Species most frequently fished for in Ohio in the previous 12 months for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (% or count as appropriate)			General Public Sample (% or count as appropriate)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Total N	132	406	539	203	192	396
In the past 12 months, which type of fish did you fish for in Ohio most frequently? (Select one.)						
Anything that bites	48.4%	37.8%	40.4%	60.8%	46.5%	53.8%
Largemouth, Smallmouth, and Spotted Bass	12.8%	18.7%	17.3%	9.2%	17.7%	13.3%
Brown, Rainbow, or Steelhead Trout	1.8%	3.4%	3.0%	1.8%	2.3%	2.1%
Catfishes	6.4%	4.6%	5.0%	9.2%	8.4%	8.8%
Crappie	6.8%	6.9%	6.8%	2.4%	1.3%	1.8%
Muskellunge or Northern Pike	0.4%	1.1%	1.0%	1.8%	1.3%	1.5%
Sunfish/Bluegill	5.0%	5.3%	5.3%	4.8%	6.7%	5.7%
Walleye, Sauger, or saugeye	12.5%	18.3%	16.9%	4.4%	10.5%	7.4%
White or Hybrid-Striped Bass	0.0%	0.8%	0.6%	1.2%	0.8%	1.1%
Yellow Perch	6.0%	3.1%	3.8%	4.4%	4.5%	4.4%

Respondents were asked to indicate the number of trips they took to pursue their most frequently targeted fish, and on average, women license holders reported taking the most trips to fish for catfishes ($M = 26.31$, $SD = 25.61$) and public women reported the most trips for Muskellunge or Northern Pike ($M = 31.33$, $SD = 31.34$). It should be noted that several species were pursued by a small percentage of license holders and/or the public, resulting in widely varying estimates (Table 9). For example, the percent of public women pursuing Muskellunge and Northern Pike was very small (1.6%, Table 9), and the average trips taken for the more frequently targeted “anything that bites” was lower across licensed ($M = 16.2$, $SD = 17.83$) and public women ($M = 11.24$, $SD = 13.55$; Table 10).

Table 10. Number of trips for species most frequently fished for in Ohio in the previous 12 months for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (Mean (SD) Median)			General Public Sample (Mean (SD) Median)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
How many [SPECIES SELECTED] fishing trips did you take in the past 12 months in Ohio? (0-100; answers greater than 100 removed from analysis). (Across all species this row, divided by species rows below.)	16 (17.4) 10	17 (16.9) 10	17 (17.0) 10	15 (19.1) 7	18 (21.9) 10	16 (20.7) 8
Anything that bites	16 (17.8) 10	17 (17.4) 11	17 (17.5) 10	12 (14.2) 7	17 (23.3) 10	15 (19.0) 8
Largemouth, Smallmouth, and Spotted Bass	16 (17.7) 10	19 (16.7) 14	19 (16.8) 13	38 (32.1) 24	20 (20.3) 9	26 (26.3) 18
Brown, Rainbow, or Steelhead Trout	5 (4.2) 6	12 (13.4) 5	11 (12.4) 5	20 (10.1) 17	20 (26.4) 13	20 (19.5) 13
Catfishes	26 (25.6) 15	18 (20.1) 10	21 (21.8) 10	10 (10.8) 6	9 (15.5) 7	10 (13.0) 6
Crappie	18 (20.4) 15	23 (19.1) 19	22 (19.3) 16	24 (28.9) 7	25 (41.0) 12	24 (29.9) 10
Muskellunge or Northern Pike	NA	21 (19.0) 20	21 (17.5) 20	40 (28.0) 36	13 (21.0) 7	29 (27.1) 23
Sunfish/Bluegill	11 (11.5) 9	13 (14.4) 8	12 (13.3) 8	5 (8.0) 2	31 (25.5) 24	20 (23.7) 10
Walleye, Sauger, or saugeye	14 (11.4) 10	16 (17.2) 10	16 (16.3) 10	13 (13.4) 10	16 (17.4) 10	15 (16.1) 10
White or Hybrid-Striped Bass	NA	6 (2.8) 6	6 (2.4) 6	5 (7.1) 3	5 (0.0) 5	7 (9.4) 4
Yellow Perch	11 (12.3) 8	8 (4.5) 8	9 (8.8) 8	14 (19.1) 6	13 (20.4) 6	14 (22.9) 5

Respondents were asked to indicate the Ohio waterbody where their most recent trip took place for their most frequently targeted fish species. Across licensed anglers, a plurality of women (45%) and men (39%) fished an Ohio inland lake or reservoir, while across the public sample responses were distributed across a few waterbodies. The most common response for public women was Pond (26%) and for men was Ohio inland lake or reservoir (28%) though Lake Erie was a close second (26%; Table 11).

Table 11. Waterbody fished on most recent trip for species most frequently fished for in Ohio in the previous 12 months for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample			General Public Sample		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
On your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for [SPECIES SELECTED], which type of water body did you fish?						
Lake Erie	20.9%	23.0%	22.5%	17.6%	25.6%	21.4%
Lake Erie Tributary	2.2%	4.9%	4.3%	1.8%	4.0%	2.9%
Ohio River	4.5%	1.6%	2.4%	18.4%	7.6%	13.1%
Ohio inland river or stream (NOT the Ohio River)	7.5%	11.1%	10.2%	7.4%	8.0%	7.6%
Ohio inland lake or reservoir	45.1%	39.1%	40.6%	19.2%	28.1%	23.5%
Pond	18.7%	19.3%	14.5%	25.2%	21.7%	23.6%
Pay Lakes	1.1%	0.8%	0.9%	10.5%	5.0%	7.8%

Respondents were asked to indicate how many of their most frequently targeted fish they caught on their most recent fishing trip, and on average, women (M = 5.92, SD = 11.35) and men (M = 5.85, SD = 6.36) license holders reported taking about the same number of fish for “anything that bites.” Notably, on average public women reported catching fewer of “anything that bites” (M = 3.86, SD = 3.70) than public men (M = 7.09, SD = 10.00; Table 12).

Table 12. Number fish caught on most recent trip targeting species most frequently fished for in Ohio in the previous 12 months for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (Mean (SD) Median)			General Public Sample (Mean (SD) Median)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
How many of your targeted fish type [SPECIES SELECTED], did you catch on this trip?						
Anything that bites	6 (11.4) 3	6 (6.4) 4	6 (8.2) 3	4 (3.7) 3	7 (10.0) 4	5 (7.2) 3
Largemouth, Smallmouth, and Spotted Bass	6 (11.0) 3	7 (10.2) 4	7 (10.2) 3	5 (4.0) 4	3 (2.4) 3	4 (3.2) 3
Brown, Rainbow, or Steelhead Trout	3 (3.1) 5	1 (1.7) 1	2 (2.0) 1	6 (2.9) 6	4 (1.7) 5	5 (2.4) 5
Catfishes	3 (2.7) 3	3 (2.5) 2	3 (2.5) 2	4 (2.8) 2	4 (5.5) 2	4 (4.2) 2
Crappie	8 (6.8) 5	13 (15.0) 10	11 (13.2) 9	6 (6.9) 2	68 (58.5) 90	27 (42.3) 7
Muskellunge or Northern Pike	NA	1 (1.0) 1	1 (0.9) 1	2 (1.1) 2	6 (2.8) 5	4 (2.7) 5
Sunfish/Bluegill	11 (9.3) 9	5 (4.7) 4	6 (6.4) 6	6 (4.7) 5	9 (4.4) 10	8 (4.7) 7
Walleye, Sauger, or saugeye	5 (4.1) 5	7 (6.3) 5	6 (6.0) 5	3 (2.2) 2	7 (8.5) 6	6 (7.2) 4
White or Hybrid-Striped Bass	NA	4 (2.8) 4	4 (2.4) 4	1 (1.9) 0	2 (NA) 2	2 (1.8) 2
Yellow Perch	17 (17.0) 10	29 (28.7) 28	24 (24.5) 14	6 (7.0) 4	18 (24.8) 9	12 (17.7) 8

Finally, respondents were asked to indicate the number of people who accompanied them on their most recent fishing trip, as well as the amount of money spent across several categories of expenditures (Table 13). Women and men across samples averaged around 2 fishing partners (excluding themselves), while average expenditures varied across samples and between men and women, though overall lodging averaged the highest level of dollars spent.

Table 13. Number of people on trip and expenditures* for most recent fishing trip for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (Mean (SD) Median)			General Public Sample (Mean (SD) Median)		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
How many people (excluding yourself) accompanied you on this trip? (0-7; answers greater than 7 removed from analysis)	2.05 (1.40)	1.96 (1.35)	2.01 (1.37)	2.23 (1.42)	2.07 (1.48)	2.15 (1.45)
Please estimate how many dollars you spent on the following supplies for your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for [SPECIES SELECTED].						
Gas for car	25.77 (52.84) 10.00	30.40 (54.08) 13.50	29.34 (53.76) 12.00	23.91 (30.94) 20.00	29.70 (37.73) 20.00	26.70 (34.39) 20.00
Gas for boat	23.41 (67.84) 0	26.77 (99.84) 0	25.98 (93.11) 0	12.56 (31.48) 0	20.73 (44.49) 0	16.42 (38.33) 0
Bait and tackle	24.14 (31.38) 15.00	38.40 (91.14) 15.00	35.06 (81.31) 15.00	21.96 (28.13) 15.00	22.16 (53.51) 11.03	22.19 (42.37) 13.88
Charter/guide	2.51 (26.16) 0	57.69 (302.53) 0	44.21 (263.84) 0	4.06 (16.50) 0	20.60 (101.37) 0	11.92 (71.23) 0
Fish processing	5.90 (30.92) 0	11.46 (41.39) 0	10.09 (39.08) 0	8.45 (28.45) 0	11.31 (53.61) 0	9.84 (42.26) 0
Boat rental/ramp fees	5.89 (35.57) 0	24.30 (138.78) 0	19.66 (121.35) 0	21.78 (138.57) 0	20.77 (63.12) 0	21.36 (109.51) 0
Groceries	26.15 (47.14) 10.00	26.49 (46.72) 10.00	26.40 (46.74) 10.00	33.40 (65.53) 10.00	46.40 (134.90) 17.32	39.51 (103.58) 15.00
Restaurants	20.87 (46.04) 0	26.51 (67.68) 0	25.13 (62.99) 0	20.71 (37.24) 0	21.32 (59.12) 0	20.98 (48.68) 0
Lodging	56.71 (263.23) 0	48.04 (213.10) 0	50.23 (226.34) 0	22.29 (85.23) 0	29.32 (110.54) 0	25.62 (97.93) 0

*Averages for this table include all \$0 responses.

Fishing perceptions

Respondents who fished in Ohio in the previous 12 months were asked to respond to several sets of items assessing their perceptions of fishing as a recreational activity. First, we asked about the level of importance of a variety of motivations for participating in fishing using a measure drawn from the leisure literature⁹. Items were averaged across their respective dimensions (i.e., escape, mastery, relational, and winning), and averages segmented by women and men for each sample are provided in Table 14. Generally, women and men were very similar in their average importance ratings within each sample, and the samples themselves shared similar trends, with the relational motivations receiving the highest importance scores across all groupings (see Appendix A for scale distribution of item responses).

Respondents answered a set of items to assess the centrality of fishing to their life, which is an indicator of their specialization and commitment to the activity¹⁰. Overall averages for the scale and item averages are provided in Table 14, while scale distribution of item responses can be found in Appendix A. On average, responses across men and women in both samples was around the midpoint of the scale (neither agree nor disagree, indicating either apathy or ambivalence). The average across all groups was in agreement with the item, “This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities that I do,” though the item measuring substitutability of fishing (i.e., “If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.”) dropped toward an average of disagreement across groups (Table 14).

⁹ Dillard, J. E., & Bates, D. L. (2011). Leisure motivation revisited: why people recreate. *Managing Leisure*, 16(4), 253–268. <https://doi-org.proxy.lib.ohio-state.edu/10.1080/13606719.2011.613624>

¹⁰ Lee, J. H., & Scott, D. (2004). Measuring Birding Specialization: A Confirmatory Factor Analysis. *Leisure Sciences*, 26(3), 245–260. <https://doi-org.proxy.lib.ohio-state.edu/10.1080/01490400490461387>

Table 14. Fishing perceptions for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (Mean (SD))			General Public Sample (Mean (SD))		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Motivations for fishing (items assessed as 1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree and averaged across scales)						
Escape	2.69 (0.81)	2.70 (0.88)	2.70 (0.86)	2.89 (0.88)	2.86 (0.87)	2.88 (0.88)
Mastery	2.42 (1.07)	2.47 (1.09)	2.46 (1.08)	2.91 (1.18)	3.01 (1.10)	2.96 (1.14)
Relational	3.40 (0.88)	3.32 (0.93)	3.34 (0.92)	3.35 (1.06)	3.11 (1.07)	3.24 (1.07)
Winning	1.56 (0.72)	1.56 (0.73)	1.56 (0.73)	1.99 (1.04)	2.14 (1.03)	2.06 (1.03)
When thinking about fishing, tell us how much you agree or disagree with the following statements. (1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree)						
This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.	4.07 (1.05)	4.15 (1.00)	4.12 (1.02)	3.93 (1.03)	3.94 (1.03)	3.94 (1.03)
Most of my friends are in some way connected to this activity.	2.99 (1.24)	3.04 (1.28)	3.02 (1.28)	3.13 (1.25)	3.03 (1.29)	3.08 (1.23)
This activity has a central role in my life.	2.96 (1.30)	3.08 (1.22)	3.04 (1.25)	3.09 (1.16)	3.06 (1.23)	3.09 (1.15)
A lot of my life is organized around this activity.	2.36 (1.26)	2.62 (1.22)	2.54 (1.24)	2.56 (1.22)	2.60 (1.22)	2.60 (1.21)
If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.	2.36 (1.31)	2.49 (1.32)	2.44 (1.32)	2.60 (1.29)	2.47 (1.32)	2.63 (1.28)

Finally, respondents were asked a series of items assessing perceptions of prejudice toward people like themselves participating in the sport¹¹, as well as the perceived safety of fishing. Averages for prejudice items for women and men across groups were all below the midpoint and reflected a general disagreement that people like themselves (as defined by the respondent) were treated differently when participating (Table 15). Safety concerns were assessed on a scale of none at all (1) to a great deal (5), and averaged highest for licensed women respondents (M = 2.71, SD = 1.30; Table 15). Respondents expressing any level of concern above “none at all” were asked to comment further on their specific concerns, and analysis by Microsoft Copilot suggested that the most frequently mentioned concerns among the licensed sample were for personal safety (see Supplementary Excel file for raw data on list of concerns entered for analysis to Copilot). Specifically, concerns centered on being alone, especially for women, the risk of crime, and encounters with strangers, as well as safety in remote or isolated areas. Among the public sample who fished, concerns centered on water safety, specifically worries about drowning, falling into the water, and the importance of wearing life jackets and other safety gear.

¹¹ Stodolska, M. (1998). Assimilation and leisure constraints: Dynamics of constraints on leisure in immigrant populations. *Journal of leisure research*, 30(4), 521-551.

Table 15. Fishing concerns for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample (Mean (SD))			General Public Sample (Mean (SD))		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
The following statements address experiences or feelings you may have had while participating in fishing. Please indicate how closely each statement reflects your experience by how much you agree or disagree. (1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree)						
People like me are treated differently when they participate.	2.09 (1.18)	1.96 (1.11)	1.99 (1.13)	2.20 (1.25)	2.26 (1.18)	2.23 (1.21)
I have never been treated differently because of my identity when participating	3.64 (1.41)	3.74 (1.45)	3.71 (1.44)	3.96 (1.16)	3.80 (1.21)	3.88 (1.19)
This activity is created for people different from me.	1.74 (1.03)	1.66 (1.03)	1.68 (1.03)	2.08 (1.21)	2.21 (1.21)	2.14 (1.21)
I choose not to participate because I am treated differently.	1.30 (0.72)	1.28 (0.71)	1.28 (0.71)	1.62 (1.06)	1.72 (1.10)	1.66 (1.08)
I often feel welcome when participating	3.94 (1.07)	4.10 (1.02)	4.06 (1.04)	4.09 (1.04)	3.90 (1.07)	4.00 (1.06)
Safety: When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? (1=None at all to 5=A great deal)	2.71 (1.30)	2.63 (1.23)	2.65 (1.25)	2.38 (1.20)	2.53 (1.34)	2.45 (1.27)

Section 3: Other outdoor recreational activities

Recreational Behavior

All respondents were asked in which of several outdoor activities they had ever participated. Aside from fishing, the most frequently selected activity was hiking/walking for men and women across both samples (Table 16). Women were less likely than men in the public sample to have participated in hunting, fishing, or camping. For the licensed respondents, women were again less likely to have participated in hunting than men, however they were slightly more likely to have camped.

Table 16. Rates of lifetime participation in outdoor activities for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample			General Public Sample		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
Have you ever participated in any of the following outdoor activities?						
Hunting	42.1%	50.0%	48.1%	10.4%	32.0%	20.7%
Fishing	98.2%	98.8%	98.6%	57.4%	70.2%	63.5%
Camping	78.6%	71.4%	73.2%	61.1%	70.1%	65.3%
Off-road motorized vehicle use	33.5%	32.9%	33.1%	17.9%	23.6%	20.6%
Shooting/Firearms practice	53.4%	57.1%	56.2%	27.6%	43.1%	35.0%
Photography	35.3%	33.9%	34.2%	38.6%	33.7%	36.3%
Hiking/Walking	80.4%	80.1%	80.2%	79.3%	76.9%	78.2%
Wildlife observation	53.4%	58.7%	57.4%	37.6%	34.2%	36.0%
Birdwatching	31.5%	29.2%	29.7%	26.6%	22.3%	24.6%
Horseback riding	28.8%	24.8%	25.8%	35.4%	25.4%	30.6%
Any other outdoor activity	13.6%	11.2%	11.8%	11.7%	11.5%	11.6%

If respondents indicated that they did not fish in Ohio in the previous 12 months, they were asked which (if any) of the other activities they did pursue in the previous 12 months (if multiple activities, respondents were asked to select the one they participated in most recently). Respondents indicating that they did not participate in any outdoor activity in Ohio in the previous 12 months were sent directly to the demographics section of the survey. Of the public who did not fish, men and women were both most likely to select hiking as their outdoor activity in Ohio in the previous 12 months, while the few license holders who did not fish (4%; Table 7) were overall most likely to select hiking as well (Table 17).

Table 17. Recent participation in outdoor activities in Ohio for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	License Holder Sample			General Public Sample		
	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men	Overall
If any, what type of recreational activity did you engage in the past 12 months in Ohio? (If multiple activities apply, select the one activity you did the most recently.)						
Camping	0.0%	11.1%	9.6%	4.8%	5.0%	4.9%
Shooting/Firearms practice	11.1%	5.6%	6.3%	2.2%	3.7%	2.9%
Photography	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.7%	9.7%	8.7%
Off-road motorized vehicle use	11.1%	0.0%	1.5%	0.1%	3.5%	1.7%
Hiking	22.2%	33.3%	31.9%	27.4%	22.9%	25.2%
Wildlife observation	22.2%	11.1%	12.6%	7.7%	6.5%	7.1%
Birdwatching	22.2%	5.6%	7.8%	8.4%	6.7%	7.6%
Horseback riding	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.6%	0.5%	0.5%
Hunting	0.0%	5.6%	4.8%	0.0%	2.5%	1.2%
Other	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.0%	5.8%	5.9%
No I did not engage in any type of recreational activity in Ohio in the past 12 months	11.1%	27.8%	25.6%	35.2%	33.2%	34.3%

Respondents were asked how many trips they took in the previous 12 months to engage in their selected activity. Licensed respondents who did not fish in Ohio are not included in further analyses for this section. Among the public sample who selected hiking as their activity (Table 18), men ($M = 11.1$, $SD = 15.3$) reported more numbers of trips on average than women ($M = 7.7$, $SD = 9.3$) and, but for birdwatchers, women ($M = 11.1$, $SD = 19.0$) reported more trips on average than men ($M = 6.7$, $SD = 6.7$). Respondents were also asked about their expenditures and how many people accompanied them on their most recent trip (Table 18). Women and men averaged just under two companions on their trip, and for both women ($M = \$65.33$, $SD = \$165.09$) and men ($M = \80.53, $SD = \$875.87$), lodging was their biggest expense on average.

Table 18. Recent trips taken to participate in outdoor activities in Ohio and average expenditures* for men and women in the license holder sample and public sample.

Item	General Public Sample (Mean (SD) Median)		
	Women	Men	Overall
How many [SELECTED ACTIVITY] trips did you take in the past 12 months in Ohio? (0-100; answers greater than 100 removed from analysis)			
Camping	9 (14.3) 5	11 (15.5) 4	10 (14.9) 4
Shooting/Firearms practice	4 (5.8) 3	8 (9.1) 3	6 (8.0) 3
Photography	9 (15.1) 2	11 (16.0) 5	10 (15.4) 4
Off-road motorized vehicle use	16 (0.0) 0	14 (18.8) 4	14 (18.3) 5
Hiking	8 (9.3) 5	11 (15.3) 5	9 (12.3) 5
Wildlife observation	7 (9.0) 3	11 (13.1) 5	9 (11.1) 4
Birdwatching	11 (19.0) 4	7 (6.7) 5	9 (15.3) 4
Horseback riding	14 (27.2) 9	2 (0.0) 2	9 (18.4) 2
Hunting	NA	15 (20.1) 5	15 (20.1) 5
Other	18 (26.3) 5	13 (15.5) 3	15 (23.5) 4
How many people (excluding yourself) accompanied you on this trip? (0-7; answers greater than 7 removed from analysis)	2 (1.4)	2 (1.5)	2 (1.4)
Please estimate how many dollars you spent on the following supplies for your most recent Ohio trip for [SELECTED ACTIVITY]			
Gas for car	25.39 (31.08) 15.00	24.65 (33.28) 10.00	25.01 (32.13) 10.00
Equipment rental fees	8.00 (32.78) 0	12.50 (54.36) 0	10.20 (44.70) 0
Groceries	34.17 (64.48) 7.00	29.37 (52.79) 10.0	31.79 (59.01) 10.00
Restaurants	30.15 (67.28) 0	26.74 (62.10) 0	28.46 (64.71) 0
Lodging	65.33 (165.09) 0	80.53 (875.87) 0	72.74 (624.66) 0

*Averages for this table include all \$0 responses.

Recreational Perceptions

Similarly to respondents who fished in Ohio in the previous 12 months, respondents reporting other outdoor activities were asked to respond to several sets of items assessing their perceptions of their chosen activity. First, we asked about the level of importance of a variety of motivations for participating in the activity using a measure drawn from the leisure literature¹². Items were averaged across their respective dimensions (i.e., escape, mastery, relational, and winning), and averages segmented by women and men for each sample are provided in Table 19. Generally, women and men were very similar in their average importance ratings (see Appendix B for scale distribution of item responses).

Respondents answered a set of items to assess the centrality of their chosen activity to their life, which is an indicator of their specialization and commitment to the activity¹³. Overall averages for the scale and item averages are provided in Table 19, while scale distribution of item responses can be found in Appendix B. On average, agreement across both women and men was generally high for the item measuring enjoyability of their chosen activity (i.e., “This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.”; Table 19), suggesting some amount of joy drawn from participation in outdoor activities broadly.

¹² Dillard, J. E., & Bates, D. L. (2011). Leisure motivation revisited: why people recreate. *Managing Leisure*, 16(4), 253–268. <https://doi-org.proxy.lib.ohio-state.edu/10.1080/13606719.2011.613624>

¹³ Lee, J. H., & Scott, D. (2004). Measuring Birding Specialization: A Confirmatory Factor Analysis. *Leisure Sciences*, 26(3), 245–260. <https://doi-org.proxy.lib.ohio-state.edu/10.1080/01490400490461387>

Table 19. Recreational perceptions for men and women in the public sample.

Item	General Public Sample (Mean (SD))		
	Women	Men	Overall
Motivations for activity (items assessed as 1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree and averaged across scales)			
Escape	2.74 (0.83)	2.76 (0.93)	2.75 (0.88)
Mastery	2.77 (1.05)	2.94 (1.11)	2.85 (1.08)
Relational	3.00 (1.10)	2.90 (1.09)	2.95 (2.09)
Winning	1.77 (0.90)	1.98 (0.93)	1.87 (0.92)
When thinking about [SELECTED ACTIVITY], tell us how much you agree or disagree with the following statements. (1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree)			
This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.	4.12 (0.90)	4.04 (0.96)	4.08 (0.93)
Most of my friends are in some way connected to this activity.	2.98 (1.22)	2.85 (1.17)	2.92 (1.20)
This activity has a central role in my life.	3.20 (1.05)	3.15 (1.10)	3.18 (1.07)
A lot of my life is organized around this activity.	2.61 (1.10)	2.59 (1.15)	2.60 (1.12)
If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.	2.64 (1.23)	2.53 (1.23)	2.59 (1.23)

Finally, respondents were asked a series of items assessing perceptions of prejudice toward people like themselves participating in the sport¹⁴, as well as the perceived safety of their chosen activity. Averages for prejudice items for women and men were all below the midpoint and reflected a general disagreement that people like themselves (as defined by the respondent) were treated differently when participating (Table 20). Safety concerns were assessed on a scale of none at all (1) to a great deal (5), and were nearly identical for men and women (Table 20). Respondents expressing any level of concern above “none at all” were asked to comment further on their specific concerns, and analysis by Microsoft Copilot suggested that the most frequently mentioned concerns were for personal safety (see Supplementary Excel file for raw data on list of concerns entered for analysis to Copilot). Specifically, concerns centered on being alone, especially for women, the risk of crime, and encounters with strangers, as well as safety in remote or isolated areas.

Table 20. Outdoor recreation concerns for men and women in the public sample.

Item	General Public Sample (Mean (SD))		
	Women	Men	Overall
The following statements address experiences or feelings you may have had while participating in [SELECTED ACTIVITY]. Please indicate how closely each statement reflects your experience by how much you agree or disagree. (1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree)			
People like me are treated differently when they participate.	2.09 (1.14)	2.19 (1.14)	2.14 (1.16)
I have never been treated differently because of my identity when participating	3.73 (1.35)	3.73 (1.25)	3.73 (1.30)
This activity is created for people different from me.	1.98 (1.15)	2.17 (1.16)	2.08 (1.17)
I choose not to participate because I am treated differently.	1.45 (0.80)	1.62 (0.95)	1.54 (0.90)
I often feel welcome when participating	3.87 (1.04)	3.85 (1.03)	3.86 (1.03)
Safety: When thinking about participating in [SELECTED ACTIVITY], to what degree are you concerned about safety? (1=None at all to 5=A great deal)	2.30 (1.13)	2.30 (1.29)	2.32 (1.21)

¹⁴ Stodolska, M. (1998). Assimilation and leisure constraints: Dynamics of constraints on leisure in immigrant populations. *Journal of leisure research*, 30(4), 521-551.

Section 4: Understanding feelings of support for level of recreation desired

In coordination with ODNR–DOW staff, we sought to probe the variation in respondents' level of felt support as it related to several other variables of interest. We assessed relationships between level of support and 1) sample, 2) gender, 3) age, 4) children in the home, 5) education, 6) income, 7) employment, 8) rurality, 9) well-being variables, and 10) perceived safety in their chosen outdoor pursuit. Recall that felt support was assessed via the single item, "To what degree do you feel supported in pursuing the amount of outdoor recreational time you would like?" on a scale of extremely unsupported (1) to extremely supported (5). We used t-tests or correlations as appropriate, and for t-test effect sizes where equal variances were not assumed, we report Glass's delta, and where equal variances were assumed, we report Cohen's *d*. Effect size interpretation for both effect size statistics are as follows: small (.2), medium (.5), and large (.8).

Respondents in the licensed sample ($M = 3.7$, $SD = 1.1$) felt significantly more supported than respondents in the public sample ($M = 3.5$, $SD = 1.0$; $t(734.9) = -2.6$, $p < 0.001$, Glass's delta = 0.15). While the effect size of this difference is small, subsequent analyses were conducted for each sample due to the known effect of sample on felt support.

Among licensed respondents, differences in felt support approached significance, such that women ($M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.1$) felt more supported than men ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.1$; $t(426) = -1.9$, $p = 0.06$, Cohen's *d* = 0.2). However, we found significant differences for women ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.0$) and men ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 1.0$) in the public sample ($t(1110) = -2.2$, $p = 0.03$, Cohen's *d* = 0.1). For licensed respondents, we found no correlation between age and felt support, however for public respondents we found a marginally significant, small correlation between age and felt support ($r(1103) = -.06$, $p = 0.05$), such that older respondents felt less supported. When considering the impact of children at home, there was no difference in the presence of children in the home and felt support for license holders; however for the public sample, respondents with any number of children at home ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.1$) felt

significantly more support than respondents with no children at home ($M = 3.5$, $SD = 1.0$; $t(1102) = -2.2$, $p = 0.03$, Cohen's $d = 0.1$).

Demographic variables like education and income sometimes impact recreational participation, and we found small effects for education for both samples, but differential effects for income for each sample. We found that higher education correlated to higher felt support ($r(1106) = .13$, $p < 0.001$) and higher income correlated with higher felt support for the public sample ($r(1104) = .20$, $p < 0.001$). For the licensed sample, there was no relationship between support and income, and in contrast to the public, lower education correlated to higher felt support ($r(423) = -.10$, $p < 0.03$). One-way ANOVA analyses comparing felt support among employed, retired, and any other response (see Table 1 for other response distributions) suggest no differences in the licensed sample. However, for the public sample, we found significantly more felt support among employed respondents ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 1.0$) when compared to retired ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 1.1$) or other respondents ($M = 3.4$, $SD = 1.1$; $F(2, 1102) = 5.9$, $p = 0.003$). We found no differences in felt support between rural and urban respondents in either sample, and likewise found no relationship between perceived safety of their chosen outdoor pursuit and felt support in either sample.

Considering the well-being variables reported in Table 5, we probed potential correlations between each item and felt support. We found no significant correlations between well-being items and felt support for the licensed sample, however, we found significant positive correlations between each well-being item and felt support for the public sample: In general, to what extent do you lead a purposeful and meaningful life? ($r(1105) = .26$, $p < 0.001$); In general, to what extent do you feel that what you do in your life is valuable and worthwhile? ($r(1106) = .28$, $p < 0.001$); To what extent do you generally feel you have a sense of direction in your life? ($r(1106) = .22$, $p < 0.001$).

Finally, we further separated responses into the following groups based on their chosen recent recreational activities in Ohio: 1) fishing; 2) hunting, off-road vehicles, shooting; 3) photography, wildlife observation, birdwatching; and 4) hiking, camping, horseback riding. We then conducted a one-way ANOVA to probe differences between groups and their felt support in their pursuit of outdoor recreation. We found the lowest felt support among the hunt/ATV/shooting group ($M = 3.2$, $SD = 1.0$) and the highest felt support among the fishing group ($M = 3.7$, $SD = 1.1$), with the photo/wildlife observation/bird group ($M = 3.5$, $SD = 1.0$) and hike/camp/horse group ($M = 3.6$, $SD = 0.9$) in between ($F(3, 1529) = 18.4$, $p < 0.001$).

Section 5: Acknowledgements

Additional Acknowledgements: We wish to acknowledge the hundreds of people that took the time to respond to our surveys, as well as ODNR–DOW staff who committed time to working through study details and provided helpful guidance throughout the project.

Contact us: For more information about this study, direct your requests to **Jeremy T. Bruskotter, Environment and Social Sustainability Lab, 210 Kottman Hall, 2021 Coffey Road, Columbus, OH, 43210.**

Appendix A. Women in Recreation in Ohio – License Summary

Important data notes are in red. Summary statistics are valid percent split by male female. Summaries for text responses where possible/appropriate are in purple. All percents given in whole numbers and means are given where appropriate. Display logic retained from Qualtrics programming in blue boxes or important survey flow noted in red throughout.

Start of Block: Introduction

Consent Thank you for your willingness to fill out this online survey on recreational activities in Ohio. Your input is invaluable to us. This survey is designed to gather your insights on recreational outdoor activities, preferences, and perceptions within the state. The summary of survey responses will play a crucial role to make decisions about the enhancement and stewardship of outdoor recreational resources in Ohio. The online questionnaire should take about 15 minutes to complete. Your participation in this survey is completely voluntary. Your input is very important to us. Your responses will only be reported in aggregate form. We will work to make sure that no one sees your survey responses without approval. But, because we are using the Internet, there is a chance that someone could access your online responses without permission. In some cases, this information could be used to identify you. This risk is minimal. Your de-identified information may be used or shared with other researchers without your additional informed consent. If you have any questions related to this survey specifically, please contact Dr. Kristina Slagle at Slagle.44@osu.edu. For questions about your rights as a participant in this study, to discuss other study-related concerns, or to lodge complaints with someone who is not part of the research team, you may contact the Office of Responsible Research Practices at 1-800-678-6251. Thank you for participating! Sincerely, Professor Jeremy Bruskotter and Dr. Kristina Slagle

Page Break

Q1.4 Below are some common sources of information about outdoor recreational opportunities. Please indicate how frequently you use the following sources to learn about outdoor recreation.

	Rarely (1)	About half the time (2)	Most of the time (3)
Television	67% 67%	25% 25%	8% 8%
Magazines	68% 77%	28% 22%	4% 1%
Websites	18% 15%	43% 49%	39% 36%
Social Media	48% 35%	32% 40%	20% 25%
Pamphlets/Brochures	67% 57%	30% 38%	3% 6%
Books	73% 77%	20% 20%	6% 4%
Podcasts	81% 85%	15% 12%	3% 3%
Community Organizations/Church	78% 84%	17% 14%	6% 2%
Work	71% 72%	21% 20%	8% 8%
Neighbors	68% 65%	28% 29%	5% 6%
Relatives	44% 40%	42% 43%	15% 18%
Friends	23% 24%	54% 52%	23% 24%

Page Break

Q1.2 Have you ever participated in any of the following outdoor activities? (*Select all that apply.*)

- Hunting 50% 42%
- Fishing 99% 98%
- Camping 71% 79%
- Off-road motorized vehicle use 33% 34%
- Shooting/firearms practice 57% 53%
- Photography 34% 35%
- Hiking/Walking 80% 80%
- Wildlife observation 59% 53%
- Birdwatching 29% 32%
- Horseback riding 25% 29%
- Any other outdoor activity (please describe) 11% 14% *Most frequent text response for men was boating, canoeing or kayaking. Women's responses were more varied, but also frequently included boating, canoeing or kayaking.*

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Q1.3 Did you go fishing in Ohio the past 12 months?

- Yes, and I purchased a license 93% 96%
- Yes, but I fished in a private lake/pond (Pay Lake) and did not purchase a license 2% 2%
- No, but I fished in another state/country 1% 1%
- No, I did not fish in Ohio or anywhere else 5% 2%

Page Break

End of Block: Introduction

Start of Block: Fishing Activity

This block was only shown to respondents who selected a “Yes” response to Q1.3. All others were sent to the Recreational Activity Filter Block. All respondents viewed the Demographics block last via survey flow programming in Qualtrics.

Q2.1 When thinking about fishing, tell us how much you feel each of the following are important reason for your participation.

	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Very important (4)	Extremely important (5)
Being alone	40% 46%	21% 20%	26% 25%	12% 8%	2% 2%
Socializing with friends	12% 17%	19% 23%	40% 33%	24% 20%	5% 6%
Pushing oneself through competition	67% 69%	14% 14%	13% 13%	6% 4%	0% 1%
Losing oneself	43% 44%	23% 24%	20% 21%	10% 9%	4% 3%
Competing	74% 73%	13% 15%	10% 8%	3% 3%	0% 1%
Reaching highest potential	44% 51%	19% 17%	19% 17%	13% 10%	5% 5%
Family activity	7% 4%	11% 8%	25% 22%	33% 34%	24% 32%
Pushing one's personal limits/pushing the envelope	54% 52%	17% 21%	18% 17%	7% 7%	4% 2%
Getting away from one's busy life	4% 4%	8% 7%	23% 21%	37% 37%	29% 32%
Making the family closer	8% 6%	12% 10%	24% 22%	31% 31%	25% 31%
Bonding with friends	7% 7%	16% 16%	30% 29%	30% 30%	17% 19%
Becoming more accomplished/better at activity	22% 22%	18% 21%	34% 25%	18% 19%	9% 15%
Escaping one's social life	31% 20%	13% 21%	22% 25%	18% 19%	16% 15%
Keeping score	75% 74%	16% 16%	7% 7%	3% 2%	0% 1%
Self-improvement	28% 30%	24% 22%	27% 26%	15% 16%	7% 6%
Personal growth and development (34)	29% 28%	21% 25%	26% 22%	14% 16%	9% 9%

Catching some fish
to eat (36)

28% 34%

19% 19%

26% 20%

15% 16%

11% 9%

Page Break

Q2.2 When thinking about fishing, tell us how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.	2% 4%	6% 6%	13% 12%	33% 38%	46% 42%
Most of my friends are in some way connected with this activity.	17% 14%	18% 25%	21% 22%	33% 29%	12% 11%
This activity has a central role in my life.	15% 19%	14% 16%	32% 28%	27% 24%	12% 13%
A lot of my life is organized around this activity.	24% 36%	20% 19%	33% 26%	16% 14%	7% 6%
If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.	32% 38%	19% 15%	25% 27%	15% 11%	9% 8%

Page Break

Q2.3 The following statements address experiences or feelings you may have had in while participating in fishing. Please indicate how closely each statement reflects your experience by how much you agree or disagree.

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
People like me are treated differently when they participate in fishing.	53% 47%	9% 10%	31% 30%	6% 10%	1% 3%
I have never been treated differently because of my identity when participating in fishing.	14% 12%	6% 10%	20% 22%	12% 14%	48% 42%
Fishing is for people different from me.	69% 62%	6% 10%	22% 24%	1% 2%	2% 2%
I choose not to participate in fishing because I am treated differently.	86% 84%	3% 5%	10% 10%	1% 1%	0% 0%
I often feel welcome when participating in fishing.	3% 4%	2% 3%	23% 26%	25% 29%	46% 38%

Page Break

Q2.4 When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety?

- None at all 20% 23%
- A little 31% 23%
- A moderate amount 25% 27%
- A lot 15% 15%
- A great deal 10% 12%

Display This Question:

If When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A little

Or When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A moderate amount

Or When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A lot

Or When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A great deal

Q2.4.1 In the box below, tell us more about what concerns you when considering going fishing.

Microsoft Copilot AI summary of responses: The most frequently mentioned concern among licensed respondents was Personal Safety. This includes worries about being alone, especially for women, the risk of crime, and encounters with strangers, as well as safety in remote or isolated areas. Many respondents emphasized the importance of feeling safe while fishing.

Page Break

Q2.5 Do you own a boat that is used for fishing? *This question allowed for multiple selections.*

No 53% 53%

Yes, paddle boat (e.g. Canoe, Kayak) 23% 23%

Yes, motor boat (i.e. anything with gasoline engine) 29% 30%

Page Break

Q2.6 How many fishing trips did you take in the past 12 months (e.g., between `#{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}` and today) to fish for **any** type of fish in Ohio? *Note: A **fishing trip** is defined as any trip where fishing occurred. Include in this count any trips that involved an overnight stay if fishing was involved.*

To answer this question, slide the circle to the number of fishing trips you took in the last 12 months. *Selecting the “More than 100” check box resulted in respondents being assigned a “not applicable” response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Page Break

End of Block: Fishing Activity

Start of Block: Filter: Species Fished

Q2.8 In the past 12 months, which type of fish did you fish for in Ohio most frequently?
(Select one.)

- Anything that bites 38% 48%
- Largemouth, smallmouth, and spotted bass 19% 13%
- Brown, rainbow, or steelhead trout 3% 2%
- Catfishes 5% 6%
- Crappie 7% 7%
- Muskellunge or northern pike 1% 0%
- Sunfish/bluegill 5% 5%
- Walleye, sauger, saugeye 18% 13%
- White or hybrid-striped bass 1% 0%
- Yellow perch 3% 6%

End of Block: Filter: Species Fished

Start of Block: Costs and Trip Data For Fishing

Q3.1 We'd like to know a bit about your recent fishing activities. In which of the following years did you fish in Ohio? *(Select all that apply.)*

- 2019 24% 31%
- 2020 24% 32%
- 2021 28% 35%
- 2022 35% 45%
- 2023 47% 60%
- All years (2019-2023) 71% 63%

Number of years purchased license according to license database:

- 1 year (2023) 28% 30%
- 2 year (2023 plus any other year 2019-2022) 18% 17%
- 3 years (2023 plus any other two years 2019-2022) 21% 20%
- 4 years (2023 plus any other three years 2019-2022) 17% 18%
- 5 years (all years 2019-2023) 16% 15%

Page Break

Q3.2 The next set of questions are about your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**.

A fishing trip for the purposes of this survey involves a trip you took where fishing was an important activity for you or family members. A trip includes all the time from leaving your residence to returning, and could include an overnight stay (e.g., a camping trip where members of your party fished in a nearby lake or river).

Q3.3 When was your most recent fishing trip in Ohio for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**? *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Year (1)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)
Month (2)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)

Page Break

Q285 How many **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips did you take in the past 12 months (e.g., between **#{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}** and today) in Ohio? *Note: A **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trip is defined as any trip where fishing for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** occurred. Include in this count any trips that involved an overnight stay if fishing for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** was involved.*

To answer this question, slide the circle to the number of **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips you took in the last 12 months. *Selecting the “More than 100” check box resulted in respondents being assigned a “not applicable” response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Number of Ohio trips in past 12 Months More than 100
17 16
0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Page Break

Q3.4 On your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for

#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}., which type of water body did you fish?

Directions: If you fished multiple water bodies, choose the one where you spent the most time.

- Lake Erie 23% 21%
- Lake Erie Tributary 5% 2%
- Ohio River 2% 5%
- Ohio inland river or stream (NOT the Ohio River) 11% 8%
- Ohio inland lake or reservoir 39% 45%
- Pond 19% 19%
- Pay Lakes 1% 1%

Page Break

Q3.5 How often did you fish each type of water body in the past 12 months (e.g., between *{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}* and today)? (Select one for each.)

	Never fished (1)	Fished rarely (1-5 times in the past 12 months) (2)	Fished occasionally (5-20 times in the past 12 months) (3)	Fished frequently (>20 times in past 12 months) (4)
Lake Erie	44% 52%	27% 26%	21% 12%	8% 10%
Lake Erie tributaries	65% 78%	17% 15%	15% 4%	4% 3%
Ohio River	83% 80%	13% 13%	3% 4%	1% 3%
Ohio inland rivers or streams (NOT the Ohio River)	42% 46%	30% 32%	20% 13%	9% 10%
Ohio inland lakes and reservoirs	24% 21%	31% 30%	24% 27%	20% 22%
Ponds	28% 27%	34% 34%	27% 24%	11% 15%
Pay lakes	92% 91%	6% 5%	1% 3%	1% 1%

Page Break

Q3.6 On the map on the following page, please provide the location of this most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**. *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Directions: *Navigate to the waterbody you fished and drop the pin at the parking location you used on this most recent trip. If you visited multiple sites, or went to multiple boat ramps and/or parking lots, on the same trip, please drop the pin at the first location you visited on this most recent trip. Please indicate the first location you fished on the trip if you walked or biked.*

Page Break

JS

Q3.6.1 Please mark your fishing location on the map above. (Note: You can zoom in or out on the map. After you drop a pin on the map, you can still move the pin if needed by dragging it). If you cannot find the location on the map, please write the name of the waterbody below. *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Page Break

Q3.7 How many of your targeted fish type, **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, did you catch on this trip?

Anything that bites 6 6
Largemouth, smallmouth, and spotted bass 7 6
Brown, rainbow, or steelhead trout 1 3
Catfishes 3 3
Crappie 13 8
Muskellunge or northern pike 1 0
Sunfish/bluegill 5 11
Walleye, sauger, or saugeye 7 5
White or hybrid-striped bass 4 NA
Yellow perch 30 17

Q3.8 Rank the importance of the following factors from 1 to 5 when choosing a fishing site for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**. *Please drag the boxes up and down to rank the importance of the factors*

_____ Water quality 3.1 3.0
_____ Fish population 2.0 2.2
_____ Site amenities 4.3 4.1
_____ Site crowding 2.7 2.9
_____ Travel distance 2.8 2.8

Page Break

Q3.9 How many people (excluding yourself) accompanied you on this trip? *Selecting the "More than 7" check box resulted in respondents being assigned a "not applicable" response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

More than 7

2 2

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Page Break

Q3.10 Please estimate how many dollars you spent on the following supplies for your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for **Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices**.

- Gas for car (\$) **\$30.40** \$25.77
- Gas for boat (\$) **\$26.77** \$23.41
- Bait and tackle (\$) **\$38.40** \$24.14
- Charter / guide (\$) **\$57.69** \$2.51
- Fish processing (\$) **\$11.46** \$5.90
- Boat rental / ramp fees (\$) **\$24.30** \$5.89
- Groceries (\$) **\$26.49** \$26.15
- Restaurants (\$) **\$48.04** \$20.87
- Lodging (\$) **\$48.04** \$56.71
- Other (\$) (11) *This entry allowed for text entry in addition to numeric entry. The most frequent response here was 0.*

End of Block: Costs and Trip Data For Fishing

Start of Block: Demographics *All respondents completed the Demographic Block last.*

Q4.1 Tell us about yourself.

In this next question set, we aim to get to know a bit more about you. This data will be used to determine how the individuals who complete this study compare with women in recreation in Ohio generally.

Meaning1 In general, to what extent do you lead a purposeful and meaningful life?

Not at all 3% 1%

1	0%	0%
2	0%	0%
3	0%	2%
4	2%	1%
5	6%	3%
6	5%	9%
7	14%	11%
8	15%	22%
9	8%	12%
Completely	46%	40%

Meaning2 In general, to what extent do you feel that what you do in your life is valuable and worthwhile?

Not at all 4% 1%

1	1%	0%
2	1%	0%
3	4%	2%
4	1%	2%
5	8%	4%
6	4%	5%
7	8%	8%
8	15%	20%
9	12%	14%
Completely	44%	45%

Meaning3 To what extent do you generally feel you have a sense of direction in your life?

Not at all 5% 1%

1 1% 1%

2 1% 0%

3 1% 1%

4 1% 3%

5 8% 11%

6 4% 7%

7 10% 14%

8 16% 15%

9 12% 14%

Completely 41% 34%

Page Break

Q4.14 How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years?

- 0 69% 66%
- 1 10% 11%
- 2 14% 13%
- 3 4% 7%
- 4 or more 3% 4%

Q4.2 What is the zip code of your home/residence? *This question was used post hoc to assign all respondents to Erie-adjacent counties or rest of Ohio counties for initial exploratory analyses. This data was frequently missing for license holders, in which case their zip code was imported from the license holder dataset.*

Page Break

Q4.3 Please indicate the extent to which you identify yourself as a/an...

	Not at all (1)	Slightly (2)	Moderately (3)	Strongly (4)	Very strongly (5)
Hunter	35% 70%	18% 12%	14% 10%	17% 2%	16% 6%
Environmentalist	16% 19%	23% 26%	32% 31%	21% 16%	9% 8%
Conservationist	9% 21%	20% 21%	30% 30%	30% 20%	12% 8%
Farmer/rancher	62% 65%	16% 14%	13% 10%	7% 8%	3% 3%
Angler/Fisherman	4% 13%	20% 32%	27% 27%	20% 16%	29% 12%

Q4.4 On average, how many hours each week do you spend doing the following? (Enter a number for each item) *Any response to these items that exceeded the total number of hours in a week was removed from analysis.*

- Paid work 32.6 32.6
- Commuting to & from paid work 4.2 5.7
- Unpaid work (e.g., housework, care work, etc.) 13.8 20.8
- Organized activities (e.g. sports) for me or my dependents 5.9 6.1
- Exercising indoors (e.g., treadmill) 2.9 4.1
- Spending time on screens outside of work (e.g., phone, TV, computer) 12.4 11.5
- Reading 5.0 6.5
- Recreating/exercising outdoors 8.2 8.0

Page Break

Q4.5 When considering the amount of time you spent participating in outdoor recreation over the past 12 months, would you prefer if it decreased, increased, or stayed the same in the next 12 months?

- Decrease 2% 3%
 - Stay the same 21% 23%
 - Increase 77% 74%
-

Q4.6 To what degree do you feel supported in pursuing the amount of outdoor recreational time you would like?

- Extremely unsupported 5% 4%
 - Somewhat unsupported 7% 10%
 - Neither supported nor unsupported 36% 21%
 - Somewhat supported 27% 30%
 - Extremely supported 26% 36%
-

Q4.7 How would you describe the residence or community where you grew up?

- Large city with 250,000 or more people 10% 10%
- City with 100,000 to 249,999 people 7% 7%
- City with 50,000 to 99,999 people 11% 13%
- Small city with 25,000 to 49,999 people 15% 17%
- Town with 10,000 to 24,999 people 17% 12%
- Town with 5,000 to 9,999 people 8% 9%
- Small town/village with less than 5,000 people 15% 16%
- A farm or rural area 18% 17%

Page Break

Q4.8 How much formal education have you completed?

- Less than high school diploma 3% 1%
- High school diploma or equivalent (for example, GED) 21% 13%
- Some college, no degree 25% 30%
- Associate's degree 11% 17%
- Bachelor's degree 22% 22%
- Graduate or professional degree 17% 17%

Page Break

Q4.9 What best describes your employment status?

- Employed (full time) 64% 63%
- Employed (part time) 3% 9%
- Care provider 0% 4%
- Unemployed (looking for work) 2% 1%
- Unemployed (unable to work) 1% 3%
- Retired 29% 16%
- Student 1% 1%

Display This Question:

If What best describes your employment status? = Employed (full time)

Or What best describes your employment status? = Employed (part time)

Q4.9.1 Does your employer provide reimbursement for personal expenses related to health, fitness, family, emotional and social wellness?

- No 54% 64%
- Yes 31% 26%
- Not sure 15% 10%

Page Break

Page Break

Q4.10 What is your annual **household** income from all sources before taxes?

- Less than \$10,000 3% 2%
- \$10,000 - \$14,999 2% 1%
- \$15,000 - \$24,999 5% 4%
- \$25,000 - \$34,999 1% 7%
- \$35,000 - \$49,999 12% 14%
- \$50,000 - \$74,999 21% 18%
- \$75,000 - \$99,999 15% 23%
- \$100,000 - \$149,999 19% 16%
- \$150,000 - \$199,999 12% 7%
- \$200,000 or more 11% 6%

Page Break

Q4.11 What year were you born? *This response was subtracted from 2024 to generate age data. Responses to this question were frequently missing from the license holder sample, and where necessary were imported from the license holder database.*

49.1 48.2

Q4.12 What is your gender? *Responses to this question were frequently missing from the license holder sample, and where necessary were imported from the license holder database. Responses of “prefer not to say” were removed from analysis for the purposes of this project.*

- Male N = 325
 - Female N = 339
 - Prefer not to say *Removed from analyses*
-

Page Break

Page Break

Display This Question:

If How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 1

Or How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 2

Or How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 3

Or How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 4 or more

Q4.15 What percentage of your recreational trips were with your kid(s)? 64% 71%

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Filter: Recreational Activity *This block was only displayed if respondents selected a "No" response to Q1.3, indicating that they did not fish in Ohio in the previous 12 months. After selecting an activity, they were sent to the Recreational Activity Block where their response activity was piped into questions to make them specific to their recent outdoor activity. After the Recreational Activity Block, they were sent to Costs and Trip Data for Other Recreational Activities Block, and then the Demographics Block where they finished the survey.*

Q5.1 If any, what type of recreational activity did you engage in the past 12 months in Ohio? (If multiple activities apply, select the one activity you did the most recently.) *Nearly all licensed respondents (97% of women and 94% of men) indicated they fished in Ohio in the previous 12 months, so we report total N for each activity below for license holders who did*

not fish and stop analyses for license holder data due to reduced data for other recreational activity items.

- Camping 2 0
- Off-road motorized vehicle use 0 1
- Shooting/firearms practice 1 1
- Photography 0 0
- Hiking 6 2
- Wildlife observation 2 2
- Birdwatching 1 2
- Horseback riding 0 0
- Hunting 1 0
- Other (please describe) 0 0

- No, I did not engage in any type of recreational activity in the past 12 months in Ohio
Respondents selecting this option were routed to the Demographics block where they finished the survey. 5 1

End of Block: Filter: Recreational Activity

Start of Block: Recreational Activity *Nearly all licensed respondents (97% of women and 94% of men) indicated they fished in Ohio in the previous 12 months, so we report total N for each activity in the filter block for license holders who did not fish. However, we do not include further analyses for other recreational activity for license holders who did not fish due to sparse data.*

Q6.1 When thinking about **{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, tell us how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Most of my friends are in some way connected with this activity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This activity has a central role in my life.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A lot of my life is organized around this activity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q6.2 When thinking about **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, tell us how much you feel each of the following are important reason for your participation.

	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Very important (4)	Extremely important (5)
Being alone	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Socializing with friends	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pushing oneself through competition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Losing oneself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Competing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reaching highest potential	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Family activity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Pushing one's personal limits/pushing the envelope	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Getting away from one's busy life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Making the family closer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bonding with friends	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Becoming more accomplished/better at activity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Escaping one's social life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Keeping score	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Self-improvement

Personal growth
and development

Page Break

Q6.3 Again considering your most recent trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following...

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
People like me are treated differently when they participate.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have never been treated differently because of my identity when participating.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
This activity is created for people different from me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I choose not to participate because I am treated differently.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often feel welcome when participating.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q6.4 When thinking about participating in **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what degree are you concerned about safety?

- None at all
- A little
- A moderate amount
- A lot
- A great deal

Display This Question:

If When thinking about participating in $\{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$, to what degree ar... = A little

Or When thinking about participating in $\{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$, to what degree ar... = A moderate amount

Or When thinking about participating in $\{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$, to what degree ar... = A lot

Or When thinking about participating in $\{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$, to what degree ar... = A great deal

Q6.4.1 In the box below, tell us more about what concerns you when considering participating in **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**.

End of Block: Recreational activity

Start of Block: Costs and Trip Data for other recreational activities

Q7.1 When was your most recent Ohio trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**?

This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.

Year (1)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)
Month (2)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)

Page Break

Q7.2 How many **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips did you take in the past 12 months (e.g., between **{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}** and today)? *Note: A **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trip is defined as any trip where **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** occurred. Include in this count any trips that involved an overnight stay if **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** was involved.*

To answer this question, slide the circle to the number of **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips you took in the last 12 months. *Selecting the “More than 100” check box resulted in respondents being assigned a “not applicable” response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Number of Ohio trips in past 12 Months More than 100

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Page Break

Q7.3 On the map below, please provide the location of the most recent Ohio trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**? *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Directions: *Navigate to the location where you participated in this activity and drop the pin at the parking location you used on this most recent trip. If you visited multiple sites, or went to multiple parking lots, on the same trip, please drop the pin at the first location you visited on this most recent trip. Please indicate the first location on the trip if you walked or biked.*

Page Break

JS

Q7.3.1 Please mark your outdoor activity location on the map above. (Note: You can zoom in or out on the map. After you drop a pin on the map, you can still move the pin if needed by dragging it). If you cannot find the location on the map, please write the name of the place below. *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Page Break

Q7.4 How many people (excluding yourself) accompanied you on this trip? *Selecting the "More than 7" check box resulted in respondents being assigned a "not applicable" response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

More than 7

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Number of participants (other than yourself)	
--	--

Page Break

Q7.5 Please estimate how many dollars you spent on the following supplies for your most recent Ohio trip for $\${Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}$.

- Gas for car (\$)
- Permits and rental fees (\$)
- Equipment rental fees (\$)
- Groceries (\$)
- Restaurants (\$)
- Lodging (\$)
- Other (\$)

End of Block: Costs and Trip Data for other recreational activities

Appendix B. Women in Recreation in Ohio – Public Summary

Important data notes are in red. Summary statistics are valid percent split by male female and weighted to reflect overall Ohio distribution (i.e., Erie subsample is downweighted; see full report for details). Summaries for text responses where possible/appropriate are in purple. All percents given in whole numbers and means are given where appropriate. Display logic retained from Qualtrics programming in blue boxes or important survey flow noted in red throughout.

Start of Block: Introduction

Consent Thank you for your willingness to fill out this online survey on recreational activities in Ohio. Your input is invaluable to us. This survey is designed to gather your insights on recreational outdoor activities, preferences, and perceptions within the state. The summary of survey responses will play a crucial role to make decisions about the enhancement and stewardship of outdoor recreational resources in Ohio. The online questionnaire should take about 15 minutes to complete. Your participation in this survey is completely voluntary. Your input is very important to us. Your responses will only be reported in aggregate form. We will work to make sure that no one sees your survey responses without approval. But, because we are using the Internet, there is a chance that someone could access your online responses without permission. In some cases, this information could be used to identify you. This risk is minimal. Your de-identified information may be used or shared with other researchers without your additional informed consent. If you have any questions related to this survey specifically, please contact Dr. Kristina Slagle at Slagle.44@osu.edu. For questions about your rights as a participant in this study, to discuss other study-related concerns, or to lodge complaints with someone who is not part of the research team, you may contact the Office of Responsible Research Practices at 1-800-678-6251. Thank you for participating! Sincerely, Professor Jeremy Bruskotter and Dr. Kristina Slagle

Page Break

Q1.4 Below are some common sources of information about outdoor recreational opportunities. Please indicate how frequently you use the following sources to learn about outdoor recreation.

	Rarely (1)	About half the time (2)	Most of the time (3)
Television	42% 38%	30% 34%	28% 28%
Magazines	73% 79%	23% 19%	4% 3%
Websites	20% 15%	46% 44%	35% 41%
Social Media	38% 22%	37% 34%	24% 44%
Pamphlets/Brochures	65% 62%	31% 32%	5% 6%
Books	70% 67%	24% 26%	6% 7%
Podcasts	76% 79%	18% 16%	6% 5%
Community Organizations/Church	74% 68%	17% 24%	9% 9%
Work	59% 65%	24% 23%	17% 12%
Neighbors	58% 47%	32% 44%	10% 9%
Relatives	37% 25%	48% 51%	15% 24%
Friends	29% 21%	49% 53%	22% 27%

Page Break

Q1.2 Have you ever participated in any of the following outdoor activities? (*Select all that apply.*)

- Hunting 32% 10%
- Fishing 70% 57%
- Camping 70% 61%
- Off-road motorized vehicle use 24% 18%
- Shooting/firearms practice 43% 27%
- Photography 34% 39%
- Hiking/Walking 77% 79%
- Wildlife observation 34% 38%
- Birdwatching 22% 27%
- Horseback riding 25% 35%
- Any other outdoor activity (please describe) 12% 12% *Most frequent text responses for men was none of the above or golf, but responses were varied. Women's responses were also varied, but frequently included swimming.*

Page Break

Q1.3 Did you go fishing in Ohio the past 12 months?

- Yes, and I purchased a license 24% 16%
- Yes, but I fished in a private lake/pond (Pay Lake) and did not purchase a license 13% 20%
- No, but I fished in another state/country 5% 4%
- No, I did not fish in Ohio or anywhere else 58% 61%

Page Break

End of Block: Introduction

Start of Block: Fishing Activity

This block was only shown to respondents who selected a “Yes” response to Q1.3. All others were sent to the Recreational Activity Filter Block. All respondents viewed the Demographics block last via survey flow programming in Qualtrics.

Q2.1 When thinking about fishing, tell us how much you feel each of the following are important reason for your participation.

	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Very important (4)	Extremely important (5)
Being alone	32% 34%	21% 21%	29% 20%	10% 11%	8% 13%
Socializing with friends	13% 7%	19% 19%	29% 29%	29% 34%	11% 10%
Pushing oneself through competition	36% 41%	19% 17%	25% 22%	15% 9%	5% 11%
Losing oneself	26% 31%	20% 21%	26% 22%	20% 16%	7% 11%
Competing	43% 49%	19% 21%	18% 15%	15% 11%	6% 4%
Reaching highest potential	24% 33%	14% 13%	23% 18%	27% 16%	13% 20%
Family activity	8% 3%	10% 7%	29% 16%	35% 34%	19% 42%
Pushing one's personal limits/pushing the envelope	31% 32%	15% 18%	30% 19%	19% 19%	6% 12%
Getting away from one's busy life	5% 2%	9% 7%	24% 21%	38% 36%	24% 34%
Making the family closer	11% 2%	9% 7%	25% 18%	30% 31%	25% 42%
Bonding with friends	8% 6%	12% 8%	29% 21%	29% 31%	22% 34%
Becoming more accomplished/better at activity	9% 20%	19% 19%	28% 22%	29% 18%	16% 23%
Escaping one's social life	13% 12%	13% 16%	27% 25%	33% 24%	14% 24%
Keeping score	46% 53%	17% 19%	15% 10%	14% 11%	8% 7%
Self-improvement	17% 19%	14% 16%	28% 22%	26% 18%	16% 25%
Personal growth and development (34)	14% 18%	16% 14%	27% 18%	27% 23%	16% 28%

Catching some fish
to eat (36)

24% 30%

13% 18%

25% 19%

26% 21%

13% 13%

Page Break

Q2.2 When thinking about fishing, tell us how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.	6% 6%	4% 10%	21% 18%	39% 39%	30% 27%
Most of my friends are in some way connected with this activity.	9% 12%	20% 17%	24% 20%	33% 33%	15% 19%
This activity has a central role in my life.	13% 16%	19% 21%	32% 31%	26% 19%	10% 14%
A lot of my life is organized around this activity.	24% 31%	18% 24%	28% 21%	22% 13%	8% 11%
If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.	20% 31%	25% 20%	18% 21%	27% 18%	10% 10%

Page Break

Q2.3 The following statements address experiences or feelings you may have had in while participating in fishing. Please indicate how closely each statement reflects your experience by how much you agree or disagree.

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
People like me are treated differently when they participate in fishing.	33% 39%	22% 18%	28% 20%	11% 15%	6% 8%
I have never been treated differently because of my identity when participating in fishing.	7% 3%	7% 13%	23% 13%	27% 27%	37% 44%
Fishing is for people different from me.	38% 44%	25% 16%	19% 25%	13% 10%	6% 6%
I choose not to participate in fishing because I am treated differently.	60% 64%	17% 14%	6% 8%	11% 7%	5% 7%
I often feel welcome when participating in fishing.	5% 4%	4% 3%	22% 16%	36% 35%	34% 43%

Page Break

Q2.4 When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety?

- None at all 24% 29%
- A little 20% 31%
- A moderate amount 23% 19%
- A lot 20% 12%
- A great deal 13% 10%

Display This Question:

If When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A little

Or When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A moderate amount

Or When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A lot

Or When thinking about participating in fishing, to what degree are you concerned about safety? = A great deal

Q2.4.1 In the box below, tell us more about what concerns you when considering going fishing.

Microsoft Copilot AI summary of responses: The most frequently mentioned fishing concern among the Qualtrics respondents was Water Safety. This includes worries about drowning, falling into the water, and the importance of wearing life jackets and other safety gear. Many respondents emphasized the need for precautions to ensure safety while near or on the water.

Page Break

Q2.5 Do you own a boat that is used for fishing? *This question allowed for multiple selections.*

No 68% 75%

Yes, paddle boat (e.g. Canoe, Kayak) 15% 13%

Yes, motor boat (i.e. anything with gasoline engine) 20% 14%

Page Break

Q2.6 How many fishing trips did you take in the past 12 months (e.g., between `#{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}` and today) to fish for **any** type of fish in Ohio? *Note: A **fishing trip** is defined as any trip where fishing occurred. Include in this count any trips that involved an overnight stay if fishing was involved.*

To answer this question, slide the circle to the number of fishing trips you took in the last 12 months. *Selecting the “More than 100” check box resulted in respondents being assigned a “not applicable” response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Page Break

End of Block: Fishing Activity

Start of Block: Filter: Species Fished

Q2.8 In the past 12 months, which type of fish did you fish for in Ohio most frequently?
(Select one.)

- Anything that bites 47% 61%
- Largemouth, smallmouth, and spotted bass 18% 9%
- Brown, rainbow, or steelhead trout 2% 2%
- Catfishes 8% 9%
- Crappie 1% 2%
- Muskellunge or northern pike 1% 2%
- Sunfish/bluegill 7% 5%
- Walleye, sauger, saugeye 11% 4%
- White or hybrid-striped bass 1% 1%
- Yellow perch 5% 4%

End of Block: Filter: Species Fished

Start of Block: Costs and Trip Data For Fishing

Q3.1 We'd like to know a bit about your recent fishing activities. In which of the following years did you fish in Ohio? *(Select all that apply.)*

- 2019 39% 33%
- 2020 39% 33%
- 2021 42% 37%
- 2022 45% 41%
- 2023 55% 54%
- All years (2019-2023) 58% 50%

Page Break

Q3.2 The next set of questions are about your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**.

A fishing trip for the purposes of this survey involves a trip you took where fishing was an important activity for you or family members. A trip includes all the time from leaving your residence to returning, and could include an overnight stay (e.g., a camping trip where members of your party fished in a nearby lake or river).

Q3.3 When was your most recent fishing trip in Ohio for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**? *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Year (1)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)
Month (2)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)

Page Break

Q285 How many **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips did you take in the past 12 months (e.g., between **#{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}** and today)? *Note: A **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trip is defined as any trip where fishing for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** occurred. Include in this count any trips that involved an overnight stay if fishing for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** was involved.*

To answer this question, slide the circle to the number of **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips you took in the last 12 months. *Selecting the “More than 100” check box resulted in respondents being assigned a “not applicable” response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Number of Ohio trips in past 12 Months More than 100
18 15
0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Page Break

Q3.4 On your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for

#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}., which type of water body did you fish?

Directions: If you fished multiple water bodies, choose the one where you spent the most time.

- Lake Erie 26% 18%
- Lake Erie Tributary 4% 2%
- Ohio River 8% 18%
- Ohio inland river or stream (NOT the Ohio River) 8% 7%
- Ohio inland lake or reservoir 28% 19%
- Pond 22% 25%
- Pay Lakes 5% 11%

Page Break

Q3.5 How often did you fish each type of water body in the past 12 months (e.g., between *{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}* and today)? (Select one for each.)

	Never fished (1)	Fished rarely (1-5 times in the past 12 months) (2)	Fished occasionally (5-20 times in the past 12 months) (3)	Fished frequently (>20 times in past 12 months) (4)
Lake Erie	38% 50%	31% 25%	23% 16%	8% 9%
Lake Erie tributaries	58% 71%	25% 19%	13% 9%	4% 2%
Ohio River	52% 54%	27% 20%	16% 18%	5% 9%
Ohio inland rivers or streams (NOT the Ohio River)	42% 50%	29% 23%	19% 19%	10% 7%
Ohio inland lakes and reservoirs	29% 32%	26% 29%	29% 23%	16% 15%
Ponds	28% 20%	27% 31%	30% 26%	16% 23%
Pay lakes	53% 58%	24% 14%	15% 14%	9% 14%

Page Break

Q3.6 On the map on the following page, please provide the location of this most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**. *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Directions: *Navigate to the waterbody you fished and drop the pin at the parking location you used on this most recent trip. If you visited multiple sites, or went to multiple boat ramps and/or parking lots, on the same trip, please drop the pin at the first location you visited on this most recent trip. Please indicate the first location you fished on the trip if you walked or biked.*

Page Break

JS

Q3.6.1 Please mark your fishing location on the map above. (Note: You can zoom in or out on the map. After you drop a pin on the map, you can still move the pin if needed by dragging it). If you cannot find the location on the map, please write the name of the waterbody below. *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Page Break

Q3.7 How many of your targeted fish type, **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, did you catch on this trip?

Anything that bites 7 4

Largemouth, smallmouth, and spotted bass 3 5

Brown, rainbow, or steelhead trout 4 6

Catfishes 4 4

Crappie 68 6

Muskellunge or northern pike 6 2

Sunfish/bluegill 9 6

Walleye, sauger, or saugeye 7 3

White or hybrid-striped bass 2 1

Yellow perch 18 6

Q3.8 Rank the importance of the following factors from 1 to 5 when choosing a fishing site for **#{Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**. *Please drag the boxes up and down to rank the importance of the factors*

_____ Water quality 2.6 2.8

_____ Fish population 2.5 2.4

_____ Site amenities 3.7 3.7

_____ Site crowding 3.2 3.3

_____ Travel distance 2.9 2.7

Page Break

Q3.9 How many people (excluding yourself) accompanied you on this trip? *Selecting the "More than 7" check box resulted in respondents being assigned a "not applicable" response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

More than 7

2 2

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Page Break

Q3.10 Please estimate how many dollars you spent on the following supplies for your most recent Ohio fishing trip to fish for **Q2.8/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices**.

- Gas for car (\$) **\$29.70** \$23.91
- Gas for boat (\$) **\$20.73** \$12.56
- Bait and tackle (\$) **\$22.16** \$21.96
- Charter / guide (\$) **\$20.60** \$4.06
- Fish processing (\$) **\$11.31** \$8.45
- Boat rental / ramp fees (\$) **\$20.77** \$21.78
- Groceries (\$) **\$46.40** \$33.40
- Restaurants (\$) **\$21.32** \$20.71
- Lodging (\$) **\$29.32** \$22.29
- Other (\$) (11) *This entry allowed for text entry in addition to numeric entry. The most frequent response here was 0.*

End of Block: Costs and Trip Data For Fishing

Start of Block: Demographics *All respondents completed the Demographic Block last.*

Q4.1 Tell us about yourself.

In this next question set, we aim to get to know a bit more about you. This data will be used to determine how the individuals who complete this study compare with women in recreation in Ohio generally.

Meaning1 In general, to what extent do you lead a purposeful and meaningful life?

Not at all 4% 1%

1 0% 1%

2 2% 1%

3 4% 1%

4 3% 5%

5 11% 12%

6 12% 10%

7 19% 16%

8 17% 18%

9 8% 11%

Completely 21% 23%

Meaning2 In general, to what extent do you feel that what you do in your life is valuable and worthwhile?

Not at all 3% 2%

1 1% 1%

2 2% 1%

3 5% 2%

4 5% 4%

5 11% 11%

6 12% 10%

7 12% 12%

8 14% 20%

9 13% 11%

Completely 22% 26%

Meaning3 To what extent do you generally feel you have a sense of direction in your life?

Not at all 5% 2%

1 1% 1%

2 2% 3%

3 4% 3%

4 6% 5%

5 11% 14%

6 9% 12%

7 11% 14%

8 17% 15%

9 11% 13%

Completely 24% 19%

Page Break

Q4.14 How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years?

- 0 77% 68%
- 1 11% 15%
- 2 7% 10%
- 3 2% 3%
- 4 or more 3% 3%

Q4.2 What is the zip code of your home/residence? *This question was used post hoc to assign all respondents to Erie-adjacent counties or rest of Ohio counties for initial exploratory analyses. This data was frequently missing for license holders, in which case their zip code was imported from the license holder dataset.*

Page Break

Q4.3 Please indicate the extent to which you identify yourself as a/an...

	Not at all (1)	Slightly (2)	Moderately (3)	Strongly (4)	Very strongly (5)
Hunter	63% 83%	14% 8%	11% 5%	7% 1%	5% 3%
Environmentalist	29% 36%	27% 29%	27% 22%	12% 6%	6% 7%
Conservationist	26% 36%	28% 29%	29% 22%	14% 8%	4% 5%
Farmer/rancher	73% 80%	11% 8%	9% 4%	4% 4%	2% 4%
Angler/Fisherman	43% 66%	21% 19%	21% 8%	8% 5%	7% 4%

Q4.4 On average, how many hours each week do you spend doing the following? (Enter a number for each item) *Any response to these items that exceeded the total number of hours in a week was removed from analysis.*

- Paid work 20.6 18.0
- Commuting to & from paid work 5.4 3.5
- Unpaid work (e.g., housework, care work, etc.) 11.1 15.6
- Organized activities (e.g. sports) for me or my dependents 4.0 3.9
- Exercising indoors (e.g., treadmill) 3.7 3.6
- Spending time on screens outside of work (e.g., phone, TV, computer) 15.5 15.4
- Reading 4.9 5.2
- Recreating/exercising outdoors 4.8 4.6

Page Break

Q4.5 When considering the amount of time you spent participating in outdoor recreation over the past 12 months, would you prefer if it decreased, increased, or stayed the same in the next 12 months?

- Decrease 7% 10%
 - Stay the same 49% 39%
 - Increase 44% 51%
-

Q4.6 To what degree do you feel supported in pursuing the amount of outdoor recreational time you would like?

- Extremely unsupported 6% 4%
 - Somewhat unsupported 8% 7%
 - Neither supported nor unsupported 40% 37%
 - Somewhat supported 29% 31%
 - Extremely supported 17% 21%
-

Q4.7 How would you describe the residence or community where you grew up?

- Large city with 250,000 or more people 18% 16%
- City with 100,000 to 249,999 people 12% 12%
- City with 50,000 to 99,999 people 14% 14%
- Small city with 25,000 to 49,999 people 16% 17%
- Town with 10,000 to 24,999 people 9% 10%
- Town with 5,000 to 9,999 people 11% 6%
- Small town/village with less than 5,000 people 10% 12%
- A farm or rural area 10% 13%

Page Break

Q4.8 How much formal education have you completed?

- Less than high school diploma 6% 4%
- High school diploma or equivalent (for example, GED) 31% 34%
- Some college, no degree 25% 26%
- Associate's degree 13% 13%
- Bachelor's degree 17% 15%
- Graduate or professional degree 8% 8%

Page Break

Q4.9 What best describes your employment status?

- Employed (full time) 37% 32%
- Employed (part time) 12% 14%
- Care provider 1% 6%
- Unemployed (looking for work) 11% 7%
- Unemployed (unable to work) 8% 11%
- Retired 30% 25%
- Student 2% 4%

Display This Question:

If What best describes your employment status? = Employed (full time)

Or What best describes your employment status? = Employed (part time)

Q4.9.1 Does your employer provide reimbursement for personal expenses related to health, fitness, family, emotional and social wellness?

- No 66% 74%
- Yes 24% 17%
- Not sure 9% 9%

Page Break

Q4.10 What is your annual **household** income from all sources before taxes?

- Less than \$10,000 10% 13%
- \$10,000 - \$14,999 7% 8%
- \$15,000 - \$24,999 9% 9%
- \$25,000 - \$34,999 11% 15%
- \$35,000 - \$49,999 18% 15%
- \$50,000 - \$74,999 20% 16%
- \$75,000 - \$99,999 14% 11%
- \$100,000 - \$149,999 7% 8%
- \$150,000 - \$199,999 2% 3%
- \$200,000 or more 1% 2%

Page Break

Q4.11 What year were you born? *This response was subtracted from 2024 to generate age data. Responses to this question were frequently missing from the license holder sample, and where necessary were imported from the license holder database.*

52.2 49.9

Q4.12 What is your gender? *Responses to this question were frequently missing from the license holder sample, and where necessary were imported from the license holder database. Responses of “prefer not to say” were removed from analysis for the purposes of this project.*

- Male N = 536
 - Female N = 576
 - Prefer not to say *Removed from analyses*
-

Page Break

Display This Question:

If How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 1

Or How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 2

Or How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 3

Or How many of your children living at your home are under the age of 18 years? = 4 or more

Q4.15 What percentage of your recreational trips were with your kid(s)? 53% 59%

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Filter: Recreational Activity *This block was only displayed if respondents selected a "No" response to Q1.3, indicating that they did not fish in Ohio in the previous 12 months. After selecting an activity, they were sent to the Recreational Activity Block where their response activity was piped into questions to make them specific to their recent outdoor activity. After the Recreational Activity Block, they were sent to Costs and Trip Data for Other Recreational Activities Block, and then the Demographics Block where they finished the survey.*

Q5.1 If any, what type of recreational activity did you engage in the past 12 months in Ohio?
(If multiple activities apply, select the one activity you did the most recently.)

- Camping 5% 5%
- Off-road motorized vehicle use 4% 0%
- Shooting/firearms practice 4% 2%
- Photography 10% 8%
- Hiking 23% 27%
- Wildlife observation 7% 8%
- Birdwatching 7% 8%
- Horseback riding 1% 1%
- Hunting 3% 0%
- Other (please describe) 6% 6%
- No, I did not engage in any type of recreational activity in the past 12 months in Ohio
Respondents selecting this option were routed to the Demographics block where they finished the survey. 33% 35%

End of Block: Filter: Recreational Activity

Start of Block: Recreational Activity

Q6.1 When thinking about **{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, tell us how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
This activity is one of the most enjoyable activities I do.	3% 2%	4% 4%	14% 12%	44% 45%	35% 37%
Most of my friends are in some way connected with this activity.	15% 16%	25% 19%	28% 24%	26% 33%	7% 8%
This activity has a central role in my life.	9% 8%	16% 14%	38% 40%	26% 29%	12% 10%
A lot of my life is organized around this activity.	24% 31%	18% 24%	28% 21%	22% 13%	8% 11%
If I couldn't do this activity, I'm not sure what I would do instead.	25% 22%	27% 27%	23% 25%	17% 19%	7% 8%

Page Break

Q6.2 When thinking about **{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, tell us how much you feel each of the following are important reason for your participation.

	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Very important (4)	Extremely important (5)
Being alone	37% 38%	17% 26%	30% 25%	13% 8%	3% 3%
Socializing with friends	21% 22%	22% 22%	29% 28%	22% 23%	6% 6%
Pushing oneself through competition	44% 53%	16% 16%	25% 14%	13% 14%	3% 4%
Losing oneself	31% 29%	23% 23%	25% 30%	16% 12%	6% 5%
Competing	62% 73%	13% 11%	19% 12%	5% 3%	1% 2%
Reaching highest potential	29% 40%	22% 22%	23% 21%	17% 12%	9% 6%
Family activity	20% 17%	18% 12%	21% 22%	24% 27%	16% 22%
Pushing one's personal limits/pushing the envelope	33% 39%	21% 22%	21% 21%	17% 14%	8% 5%
Getting away from one's busy life	8% 6%	12% 10%	21% 23%	31% 40%	28% 22%
Making the family closer	18% 19%	17% 11%	28% 24%	21% 27%	17% 20%
Bonding with friends	18% 21%	21% 18%	27% 24%	20% 23%	13% 14%
Becoming more accomplished/better at activity	20% 24%	21% 25%	25% 26%	22% 19%	13% 7%
Escaping one's social life	26% 23%	17% 18%	26% 25%	21% 25%	10% 10%
Keeping score	68% 79%	14% 10%	13% 8%	2% 2%	3% 2%
Self-improvement	17% 15%	11% 15%	31% 32%	23% 21%	18% 16%
Personal growth and development	13% 13%	13% 16%	33% 29%	23% 26%	18% 16%

Page Break

Q6.3 Again considering your most recent trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following...

	Strongly disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)
People like me are treated differently when they participate.	39% 48%	18% 10%	30% 31%	11% 11%	3% 2%
I have never been treated differently because of my identity when participating.	8% 10%	8% 8%	23% 23%	26% 16%	35% 43%
This activity is created for people different from me.	41% 50%	17% 13%	31% 28%	8% 4%	4% 5%
I choose not to participate because I am treated differently.	66% 72%	10% 11%	19% 15%	4% 1%	0% 1%
I often feel welcome when participating.	3% 5%	6% 1%	28% 28%	30% 34%	33% 32%

Page Break

Q6.4 When thinking about participating in **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what degree are you concerned about safety?

- None at all 36% 27%
- A little 26% 32%
- A moderate amount 21% 26%
- A lot 8% 10%
- A great deal 10% 5%

Display This Question:

*If When thinking about participating in **#{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what degree ar... = A little*

*Or When thinking about participating in **#{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what degree ar... = A moderate amount*

*Or When thinking about participating in **#{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what degree ar... = A lot*

*Or When thinking about participating in **#{q://QID208/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**, to what degree ar... = A great deal*

Q6.4.1 In the box below, tell us more about what concerns you when considering participating in **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**.

Microsoft Copilot AI summary of responses: The most frequently mentioned concern among Qualtrics respondents participating in other outdoor recreation was Personal Safety. This includes worries about being alone, especially for women, the risk of crime, and encounters with strangers, as well as safety in remote or isolated areas. Many respondents emphasized the importance of feeling safe while engaging in outdoor activities.

End of Block: Recreational activity

Start of Block: Costs and Trip Data for other recreational activities

Q7.1 When was your most recent Ohio trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**?
This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.

Year (1)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)
Month (2)	▼ 2023 (1) ... (12)

Page Break

Q7.2 How many **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips did you take in the past 12 months (e.g., between **#{date://OtherDate/FL/-1%20year}** and today)? *Note: A **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trip is defined as any trip where **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** occurred. Include in this count any trips that involved an overnight stay if **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** was involved.*

To answer this question, slide the circle to the number of **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}** trips you took in the last 12 months. *Selecting the “More than 100” check box resulted in respondents being assigned a “not applicable” response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Number of Ohio trips in past 12 Months More than 100

119

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Page Break

Q7.3 On the map below, please provide the location of the most recent Ohio trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**? *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Directions: *Navigate to the location where you participated in this activity and drop the pin at the parking location you used on this most recent trip. If you visited multiple sites, or went to multiple parking lots, on the same trip, please drop the pin at the first location you visited on this most recent trip. Please indicate the first location on the trip if you walked or biked.*

Page Break

JS

Q7.3.1 Please mark your outdoor activity location on the map above. (Note: You can zoom in or out on the map. After you drop a pin on the map, you can still move the pin if needed by dragging it). If you cannot find the location on the map, please write the name of the place below. *This question was used for economic analyses not relevant to the present objectives.*

Page Break

Q7.4 How many people (excluding yourself) accompanied you on this trip? *Selecting the "More than 7" check box resulted in respondents being assigned a "not applicable" response value of -99, identical to if they had skipped or not seen the question.*

Page Break

Q7.5 Please estimate how many dollars you spent on the following supplies for your most recent Ohio trip for **#{Q5.1/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices}**.

- Gas for car (\$) **\$24.65** \$25.39
- Permits and rental fees (\$) *This entry allowed for text entry in addition to numeric entry. The most frequent response here was 0.*
- Equipment rental fees (\$) **\$12.50** \$8.00
- Groceries (\$) **\$29.37** \$34.17
- Restaurants (\$) **\$26.74** \$30.15
- Lodging (\$) **\$80.53** \$65.33
- Other (\$) *This entry allowed for text entry in addition to numeric entry. The most frequent response here was 0.*

End of Block: Costs and Trip Data for other recreational activities

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